

Timber constructions: a report on the status and potential of development potential of timber construction elements

Project Acronym	BIGWOOD
Extended Project title	BIGWOOD - Reducing barriers and prejudices about multi-storey timber buildings through the creation of design awareness
Project Number	ITAT1081
Lead Partner	Libera Università di Bolzano – Freie Universität Bozen
Project Duration	38 Month
Project Start	01 October 2019
Project End	20 December 2022
Deliverable No.	D.4.1-D.4.2
Deliverable Title	Timber constructions: a report on the status and potential of development potential of timber construction elements
Work Package	WP 4 – Building and implementing an environment for research and technical development between the partners of the University
Related Activity	Task 4.1,4.2,4.3
Responsibility	Free University of Bozen - Bolzano

Contents

1	Introduction.....	5
2	State of the Art and Literature research	6
2.1	INTRODUCTION	6
2.2	BIBLIOMETRIC RESEARCH	10
2.2.1	Bibliometric networks.....	10
2.2.2	Research databases.....	14
2.2.3	Numerical approaches analysis.....	19
2.3	Selection of inherent papers	21
2.4	Results and Discussion	25
2.4.1	Georeferenced and topics distribution	25
2.4.2	Discussion of the literature results	26
2.4.3	Cross Laminated Timber.....	44
2.5	Comments and Remarks	45
3	ACOUSTIC PERFORMANCE TESTING OF PARTITIONS	47
3.1	Introductions to the Laboratories	47
3.2	Acoustic characterization of partitions	51
3.3	Results on insulating materials for floors	53
3.3.1	Results of the parallel measurements at the Free University of Bozen and at the University of Innsbruck.	53
3.4	Results on insulating materials for floors	57
3.4.1	First group.....	57
3.4.2	Second group	60
3.4.3	Third group	62
3.4.4	Fourth group.....	64
3.5	Results on insulating materials for walls	67
3.5.1	First group.....	67
3.5.2	Second group	68
3.5.3	Third group	69
4	THERMAL SIMULATION ON INDOOR COMFORT	71
4.1	Preliminary consideration on simulation	71
4.2	Description of materials to meet the minimum requirements for each standard.....	73
4.2.1	AUSTRIA	73

4.2.2	CASACLIMA	74
4.2.3	ITALY.....	74
4.2.4	BIGWOOD PROPOSAL.....	75
4.3	Energy consumption simulation.....	76
4.4	Indoor Comfort simulation.....	80
4.5	Remarks and comments	83
5	CONCLUSION.....	84
6	References.....	85

List of Tables

Table 1:	List of the material properties necessary for the thermal and acoustic insulation simulations.....	24
Table 2:	summary of the parameters characterizing the Timber Stud	27
Table 3:	summary of the parameters characterizing the OSB.....	28
Table 4:	summary of the mechanical and thermal parameters characterizing the rock wool	29
Table 5:	summary of the mechanical and acoustic parameters characterizing the rock wool	31
Table 6:	summary of the mechanical and thermal parameters characterizing the glass wool	32
Table 7:	summary of the mechanical and acoustic parameters characterizing the glass wool	33
Table 8:	summary of the parameters characterizing the XPS	34
Table 9:	summary of the parameters characterizing the EPS	34
Table 10:	summary of the parameters characterizing the foam glass	35
Table 11:	summary of the parameters characterizing the foam glass	36
Table 12:	summary of the parameters characterizing the hemp	36
Table 13:	summary of the parameters characterizing the cellulose	37
Table 14:	summary of the parameters characterizing the straw.....	38
Table 15:	summary of the parameters characterizing the wood fiber.....	39
Table 16:	summary of the parameters characterizing the date palm fiber	39
Table 17:	summary of the parameters characterizing the cork	40
Table 18:	summary of the parameters characterizing the coconut fiber	40
Table 19:	summary of the parameters characterizing the jute	41
Table 20:	summary of the parameters characterizing the kenaf	42
Table 21:	summary of the parameters characterizing the cotton	42
Table 22:	summary of the parameters characterizing the flax	42
Table 23:	summary of the parameters characterizing the polyurethane foam	43
Table 24:	summary of the parameters characterizing the kraft.....	44
Table 25:	summary of the parameters characterizing the CLT.....	44
Table 26:	Building simulation settings.	72

List of Figures

Figure 1:	Analysis of most used keywords in research papers dealing with timber construction elements. “Cross laminated” and “timber frame” are within white circles, whether “finite element method” is the purple one to highlight their positions.	7
-----------	--	---

Figure 2: Analysis of repetition of keywords and overlay of the association strengths of “Timber frame thermal”	11
Figure 3: Analysis of repetition of keywords and overlay of the association strengths of “Timber frame sound”	12
Figure 4: Analysis of repetition of keywords and overlay of the association strengths of “Cross Laminated Timber thermal”	13
Figure 5: Analysis of repetition of keywords and overlay of the association strengths of “Cross Laminated Timber sound”	14
Figure 6: Collection procedure’s scheme for the “Timber Frame” keyword both for the “performance” side (left) and for the “simulation” side (right)	15
Figure 7: Collection procedure’s scheme for the Cross Laminated Timber both for the “performance” side (left) and for the “simulation” side (right)	16
Figure 8: Rating analysis of Timber Frame thermal performance/simulation/characterization from Google Scholar	17
Figure 9: Rating analysis of Timber Frame thermal performance/simulation/characterization from Scopus	17
Figure 10: Rating analysis of Timber Frame acoustic performance/simulation characterization from Google Scholar	18
Figure 11: Rating analysis of Timber Frame acoustic performances characterization from Scopus	18
Figure 12: Rating analysis of Cross Laminated Timber performance/simulation characterization from Google Scholar	19
Figure 13: Rating analysis of Cross Laminated Timber performances characterization from Scopus	19
Figure 14: Analysis of most used keywords in research papers for timber construction both for acoustic (left) and thermal insulation (right)	20
Figure 15: Topics treated in the sample of papers collected	25
Figure 16: Geographic distribution of the papers collected - continental division (left) and nationality division (right)	26
Figure 17: Ceiling test stand at the University of Innsbruck	47
Figure 18: Upper and lower part (left and middle), hydraulic cylinder to lift the floor (right)	48
Figure 19: Threaded rods for pre-tension applications	48
Figure 20: Two-storey test stand at the University of Innsbruck	49
Figure 21. Three chamber set-ups at the Free University of Bozen	50
Figure 22: CLT under examination from the receiving room (downstairs)	51
Figure 23: CLT floor coupled with concrete slab and insulating material	51
Figure 24: Sound reduction index	54
Figure 25: Normalized impact sound pressure level	55
Figure 26: Impact sound pressure level (rubber ball)	56
Figure 27: First group – Sound reduction index	58
Figure 28: First group - Normalized impact sound pressure level	59
Figure 29: First group - Impact sound pressure level (rubber ball)	59
Figure 30: Second group – Sound reduction index	61
Figure 31: Second group - Normalized impact sound pressure level	61
Figure 32: Second group - Impact sound pressure level (rubber ball)	62
Figure 33: Third group – Sound reduction index	63
Figure 34: Third group - Normalized impact sound pressure level	63
Figure 35: Third group - Impact sound pressure level (rubber ball)	64
Figure 36: Fourth group – Sound reduction index	65

Figure 37: Fourth group - Normalized impact sound pressure level	66
Figure 38: Fourth group - Impact sound pressure level (rubber ball)	66
Figure 39: First group - walls: Sound reduction index	68
Figure 40: Second group - walls: Sound reduction index	69
Figure 41: Third group - walls: Sound reduction index	70
Figure 42: Perspective of the standard open office space	71
Figure 43: Area of the Italy-Austria Interreg Project	72
Figure 44: Wood construction that fulfills the minimum requirements of the Austrian OIB-6 regulation.	73
Figure 45: Wood construction that fulfills the minimum requirements of the CasaClima certification system.	74
Figure 46: Wood construction that fulfills the minimum requirements of the Italian DM 26.06.2015 regulation for the climate zone F.	75
Figure 47: Wood construction that fulfills the minimum requirements of proposal of the Bigwood project.	75
Figure 48: Energy consumption estimation for the 4 different requirements - Bozen site	76
Figure 49: Energy consumption estimation for the 4 different requirements - Udine site	77
Figure 50: Energy consumption estimation for the 4 different requirements - Vicenza site	78
Figure 51: Energy consumption estimation for the 4 different requirements - Innsbruck site	79
Figure 52: PMV Cumulative duration Plot - Bolzano	81
Figure 53: PMV Cumulative duration Plot - Udine	81
Figure 54: PMV Cumulative duration Plot - Vicenza	82
Figure 55: PMV Cumulative duration Plot - Innsbruck	82

1 Introduction

The following report will highlight the main results obtained from the Italy - Austria Interregional collaboration developed within the Interreg Project BIGWOOD on research and development of timber buildings, existing projects concerning timber buildings and on the state of the art of scientific research and construction. In this context, it will be then highlighted how the characterization of the materials plays a fundamental role both in determining the acoustic and thermal performance.

2 State of the Art and Literature research

2.1 INTRODUCTION

The environmental advantages of timber buildings and their construction processes are worldwide acknowledged [1] - [3]. Wood is one of the most eco-friendly raw resource, suitable for construction and characterized by (i) wide availability in nature and (ii) relative ease of handling [4]. It is a cutting-edge material thanks to environmental friendliness and with a broad scope of end-reuses. Moreover, wood can be used in several phases of the construction process [5]. It is bio-degradable [6], sustainable [7] and recyclable [8]. Wooden elements are an ecological resource compared to other similar products based on different materials [9]. These characteristics are the main reasons for its wide diffusion. Indeed, it can be used either directly in the building structure or as an element of other subsystems, such as floors, roofs and wall or façades [10].

The building sector is accountable for 42% of final energy consumption, 35% of total green gas (GHG) emission, 50% of the extracted materials utilization and 30% of the water consumption in the European Union [11]. Environmental construction impacts are associated with material renewability and recyclability [12]. In the selection and evaluation process of alternative sustainable materials, several criteria have to be considered including stability, durability, environmental impact, speed of erection, cost, availability and delivery time [13]. Thus, timber buildings imply lower Global Warming Potential and consequential benefits on Life Cycle Assessment [14]. In addition, even if timber structures can respond to all open issues, worldwide the prejudices on Multi-Storey Wooden Buildings (MSWB) are still strong [15], even if in many countries of the Northern Hemisphere, wooden edifices are the most widely acknowledged constructions, due to their economical and practical qualities [16] and contribute to social well-being [17].

At present, a large number of studies has been focused on wood properties for construction purpose and various types of building solutions were engineered [18]. To understand the topics trends, research was conducted to understand which are currently the most diffused timber construction techniques. In Figure1, it is possible to notice the result of research using Scopus, where the most present keywords related to timber building are used when searching for “timber construction elements”. In the centre, the most used keyword is highlighted in yellow, where the other ones are presented far way, featuring a fading background when less used. Among all the

results, it is possible to note that the only keywords related to wooden construction elements are “Cross Laminated” (top-left) and “timber frames” (bottom-left). Thus, these main timber elements are not only more widely researched, but also used in the market. Furthermore, the “finite element method” is also present, highlighting the existence of numerical simulation related to this topic.

Figure 1: Analysis of most used keywords in research papers dealing with timber construction elements. “Cross laminated” and “timber frame” are within white circles, whether “finite element method” is the purple one to highlight their positions.

Nevertheless, when undergoing a literature review on these topics, one can find a notable segmentation of research, focusing only on some of the potential timber constructions properties [19]. Special attention was paid to the issue of simulation, which permits to avoid construction accidents, limits the uncertainties and addresses issues before the construction site has even started, avoiding constant and time-consuming site visits [20]. This tool is now a common practice among engineers and architects [21].

Computational building performance modelling and simulation is a multidisciplinary, problem-oriented and wide-in-scope procedure [22]. Computational simulation is one of the most powerful analysis and avant-garde development tools for experts in our world [23]. Wang and Zhaib [24]

provided an overview of Building Programs Simulation advancements and trends for development and application between 1987 and 2014. They focused on six different topics [25] finding that the trend of interest in coupled simulation has grown in the last years. Indeed, due to some common properties, studies on thermal and acoustic analyses [26],[27] and simulations [28] are increasingly diffused, but not always converging. Thus, building simulation is an essential tool for trying out different solutions and interchanging insulation layers before construction. This step is crucial in the decision-making process of thermal and sound insulation, where the layers of the walls have to be carefully chosen not only to optimize the spaces but also to ensure a good quality of both thermal [29] and acoustic [30] comfort for users.

With attention to timber buildings, some authors simulated their efficiency to test the performance and the thermal insulation and comfort [31] - [35]. Furthermore, the application of building simulation on thermal insulation is widely used also to estimate the long terms effects of future solutions [36] or to test new potential insulation solution that may be improved. These procedures could be used also to understand the behaviour of a newly marketed product or material and assess its potential for inclusion in the project [37]. Moreover, in the thermal insulation evaluation and simulation, it is important to consider the influence of the materials location [38] to test the design and the used materials correctly.

Another well-suited topic is sound insulation and acoustic performance of walls. In this case, simulations are useful tools to perform and compare different numerical modelling of complex building elements [39], in order to compare different approaches on evaluation methods [40] and to test new materials and their future application in building sector [41]. As for the thermal, also in acoustic field simulations are used to test the performance of several multilayers options [42] or to perform timber construction in new perspectives [43].

It is also interesting to note that also several funded international projects dealt with these topics. This demonstrates how these issues are of interest to scientists, public and private institutions and practitioners. Accordingly, the European Union encourages sustainable building development [44],[45]. As examples, some projects focused on the thermal and acoustic performances of timber elements are listed below:

- FormaWood [46] is an Interreg project based in the Wallonia region between France and Belgium which mainly aimed to highlight the difference between the thermal and

acoustic standards in the two countries involved and to simulate passive and energy-efficient construction [47];

- NERO project [48] aims to show the cost reduction of nearly zero-energy wooden buildings through demonstration projects that include both residential and non-residential individual buildings with a focus on the LCA;
- Build in wood project [49] main aim is focused on thermal efficiency perspective and it develops a structural and customizable construction system platform and guidelines for incorporating ICT tools in the design process.

Simulation approaches need robust and reliable inputs [50], focusing on materials characterization [51]. Attention to this issue is crucial not also in structural [52], but also in thermal [53] and acoustic [54] applications. Timber buildings thermal and acoustic simulations are present in literature, but not always focused on the same issues. They are often based on building envelope, but a clear understanding of reliability and robustness of selected used data is still unclear.

Conversely, numerical simulations focused on seismic issues present high reliability. The reliability of the seismic simulations is well known [55] - [60] and the results are based on parameters that have been validated by the technical and scientific community in years [61] - [64]. The same conclusion can be applied to fire-resistance simulations [65] - [69].

In this perspective, the aims of this paper are to:

- assess if there is a clear link between numerical simulation and materials characterization or, conversely, these two procedures are managed and developed separately in scientific papers;
- investigate if there is a variability of materials parameters, basing on the available data contained in past research;
- provide an overview of the main physical parameters used in numerical thermal and acoustic insulation simulations of timber walls;
- draw a critical analysis related to parameters detected by discussing the reliability of the data, the range of variability and the role in the simulation procedure.

Hence, it will be possible to understand the availability of these parameters and their variability in literature. The discussed issues will highlight where the availability of information is concentrated. To this aim, the adopted procedure used to gain, collect and study all the physical

parameters is shown. The needed elements for the simulation and computational phase of timber building elements are also depicted. A brief introduction of the more diffused computational methodologies from the thermal and acoustic insulation point of view is then provided, followed by an in-depth analysis of the research outputs.

2.2 BIBLIOMETRIC RESEARCH

2.2.1 Bibliometric networks

This section aims to collect papers and studies focused on the characterization of materials for future simulation phases and to understand if there is a strong connection between materials characterization and simulation, considering timber constructions.

Thus, VosViewer was used to build graphic schemes, including connections between keywords. The bubbles dimension indicates the most used keywords, the width of the lines expresses the number of co-citation and connection of a selected keyword. The topics are organized by cluster, each primary colour, based on the RGB model, identifies a specific cluster, identified by the software algorithm [70]. The investigation is repeated for four analysis, one for each typology of construction technique individuated in Figure 1 (Cross Laminated Timber, CLT, or Timber Frame, TF) and one for each main topic (acoustic and thermal insulation).

2.2.1.1 *Timber Frame*

In Figure 2 the first investigation results are reported for the keywords “Timber frame thermal”. It is highlighted that mineral wool is the mostly cited insulation material. This could be justified by the great availability on the market and the wide use of this material from 2010 onwards for thermal, acoustic and mostly for fire resistance purposes [71]. When focusing on thermal properties, it appears that the analyses related to the thermal conductivity are the most commonly characterized. Nevertheless, the dimensions of the thermal conductivity bubble highlight that a relatively small number of works faces this topic. Finally, almost a third of the papers focus on energy efficiency related to sustainability and environmental issues (red bubbles). A further one-third deals with building techniques (green bubbles), and only the remaining part focuses on the thermal issues.

Figure 2: Analysis of repetition of keywords and overlay of the association strengths of “Timber frame thermal”.

On the other hand, when we focus on the acoustic topic, things change. Results are depicted in Figure 3 for the keywords “Timber frame sound”. It is possible to note that sporadically “acoustic” and “sound propagation” are related to “Finite Element Method”. Moreover, focusing on green bubbles, it is possible to see that among the keywords used, there is also a connection with “thermal insulation”. This means that these two topics sometimes are treated in the same papers, highlighting their interconnection related to timber frame construction technique. Another important issue is related to materials characterization: “acoustic variables control” appears as a frequently investigated topic mostly cross-linked with “timber”, “architectural acoustics”, “acoustic noise” and “laboratory measurements”. This implies that materials take part almost always when facing general topics, more rarely when facing sound insulation, which is more related to “acoustic waves”. However, this latter topic intrinsically considers materials properties.

Figure 3: Analysis of repetition of keywords and overlay of the association strengths of “Timber frame sound”.

2.2.1.2 *Cross Laminated Timber*

In Figure 4, the connection web of the keywords related to the “Cross Laminated Timber thermal” is shown. The most diffused keywords are related to CLT referring to the composition of the structural element, (e.g. “laminating”, “cross-laminated”, “CLT”), followed by the ones referred to fire resistance capacities and fire protection. As for Timber Frame, here again, the only thermo-physics characterization found among the keywords seems to be the thermal conductivity (blue), which also is included in “thermodynamic properties”. Anyway, these two are not related to “thermal insulation”, “energy efficiency”, “thermal performances”, etc. (red bubbles), meaning that studies focused on thermal characterization are separated from the ones managing the overall building thermal comfort and efficiency. This demonstrates how the studies on these topics are fragmented.

Figure 5: Analysis of repetition of keywords and overlay of the association strengths of “Cross Laminated Timber sound”

2.2.2 Research databases

The results of the previous sections are used here as inputs for the research databases definition, namely Google Scholar and Scopus. Thus, the first keywords used are related to the construction elements most found in literature (“Timber Frame” or “Cross Laminated Timber”) in combination with different physical characterization requirements, like “thermal performance/simulation”, “sound performance/simulation”, “noise performance/simulation” and also with the keyword “insulation” (i.e. “sound insulation performance”). The output of this phase is intended to highlight the differences in the number of papers and proceedings available in the two web search engines. The collection process of the different steps for the timber frame is depicted in Figure 6. In this, it is possible to see how in Scholar among the totality approaching the Timber Frame, only the 35,8% describes its performance, while the 7,4% approach to the simulation. Then, in Scopus higher percentages meet the keywords selected: the 68,3% of papers describe the performance of TF, while the 8,5% describe the simulation approach. Then, having a deeper analysis in the thermal and acoustic topics, it is possible to see how both for the adoption of “performance” and “simulation” keywords, the thermal topic is more treated by Scopus, conversely the acoustic topic (sound and noise) is slightly more treated by Scholar.

Figure 6: Collection procedure’s scheme for the “Timber Frame” keyword both for the “performance” side (left) and for the “simulation” side (right)

Figure 7 presents the collection process related to CLT with the same process and same behaviour found for the Timber Frame. Indeed, also in this case the Scopus rates are significantly higher. Indeed, Scholar among the totality approaching the CLT, only the 22,3% describes its performance, while the 5,8% approach to the simulation. Then, in Scopus the 35,2% of papers describe the performance of CLT, while the 9,3% describe the simulation approach. Then, have a deeper analysis in the thermal and acoustic topics, it is possible to see how, conversely for what happened for TF, both for the adoption of “performance” and “simulation” keywords, both the thermal topic and the acoustic topic (sound and noise) are more treated by Scholar, highlighting how the CLT characterization in these two fields is more diffused in the Scholar database with significantly higher percentages than in Scopus.

Figure 7: Collection procedure's scheme for the Cross Laminated Timber both for the “performance” side (left) and for the “simulation” side (right)

Furthermore, the papers were divided into chronological order, based on the publication year using both Scopus and Google Scholar databases. The chronological division is based on the decade of publishing. This procedure shows if these issues are of some interest in years and if the two databases agree.

The percentage ratings and the information acquired by the research will be depicted firstly for Timber frame and finally for Cross Laminated Timber. The results presentation will be focused firstly on thermal then on acoustic insulation. In the end, these two aspects will be merged for a complete database.

2.2.2.1 Timber Frame.

The chronological division is based on the decade of publishing. The results are depicted, for the Google Scholar outputs, in Figure 8 for the thermal and Figure 10 for the acoustic approach. The Scopus sorting is shown in Figure 9 for the thermal and Figure 11 for the acoustic issue. Papers before the decade 1970-1980 were not included.

It is evident how the papers in Google Scholar dealing with the thermal insulation are widely available. Particularly, it can be observed in both cases that an increasing trend of publications is

present related to the two last decades, highlighting that there is a clear technical improvement of technologies, software and simulation's tools (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Rating analysis of Timber Frame thermal performance/simulation/characterization from Google Scholar

From Figure 9, it can be seen how the trends founded in Scopus are similar to the Google Scholars ones. Still, the numbers of papers available are noteworthy lower using both the keyword “performance” and “simulation”.

Figure 9: Rating analysis of Timber Frame thermal performance/simulation/characterization from Scopus

Figure 10 shows the Google Scholar outcome from the acoustic point of view. Firstly, it is remarkable to note that in the last two decades the topics related to the acoustic of the timber frame have significantly increased. Accordingly, these trends show a constant increase in the number of papers published and thus an interest in the subject.

Figure 10: Rating analysis of Timber Frame acoustic performance/simulation characterization from Google Scholar

As in the case of the thermal outcome from Scopus, as shown in Figure 11, a lower amount of research is available in this online database. Anyway, the positive time trend is confirmed.

Figure 11: Rating analysis of Timber Frame acoustic performances characterization from Scopus

2.2.2.2 Cross Laminated Timber

The results are depicted for the Google Scholar outputs in Figure 12 both for the thermal and the acoustic topics. The Scopus outputs are illustrated in Figure 13. Papers before 1980 were not included as mentioned in the case of Timber frame.

How can be seen in Figure 12, the interest in Cross Laminated Timber has clearly grown up in this last decade. Then, paying attention to the distinction between the two outputs related to the two keywords, it is noticeable that papers related to “simulation” are higher than the outcome related to “performance”. This could be related to the increase of new simulation tools developed from 2000. Another interesting result is connected to the acoustic field. Indeed, the papers featuring “noise” as keyword in combination with “performance” are more present than the papers coming from the same research field but featuring the keyword “simulation”.

Figure 12: Rating analysis of Cross Laminated Timber performance/simulation characterization from Google Scholar

The Scopus results, depicted in Figure 13, always show that the new interest in the topic is developed only in the last decade. Thus, all the papers before 2010 rarely deal with thermal and acoustic issues.

Figure 13: Rating analysis of Cross Laminated Timber performances characterization from Scopus

It can, therefore, be deduced that the two databases show large differences in the availability of academic articles in the case of CLT. Even if the results for individual searches contrast with each other in terms of the used keywords, it is still evident that Google Scholar shows more results for academic searches. This means that, in this field, research present their results mostly using conference proceedings, reports, projects deliverables which are not often indexed in Scopus.

2.2.3 Numerical approaches analysis

Here, an investigation was conducted, in order to retrieve the most used numerical models in the fields of acoustic and thermal insulation related to timber construction. In Figure 14, it is highlighted that the most diffused acoustic approaches are the Finite Element Method (top - center and bottom - left), followed by the Transfer Matrix Method (down-right). For the thermal

insulation, the Finite Elements Method appears to be always preferred (top – right). Conversely, neither of these appears to mention the Statistical Energy Analysis (SEA) or Boundary Element Method. However, there is evidence that in acoustics for the high frequencies SEA is often used [73]. Thus, it will be comprised in this research.

Figure 14: Analysis of most used keywords in research papers for timber construction both for acoustic (left) and thermal insulation (right)

Despite this, in both acoustic and thermal insulation fields, as remarked by Figure 14, the most used method for the thermal analysis is the Finite Elements Method [74] - [76], as well as for the acoustic insulation, [77] - [79]. However, if from one side in the thermal applications FEM requires only two parameters (c_p and λ) of inputs coupled with density and short computation times [80], on the other in acoustics a higher number of required input parameters are needed [81] and at least six elements per wavelength have to be considered for the mesh creation [82], implying longer computation times. For these reasons, despite the physical accuracy of FEM, often it is computationally expensive [83]. Conversely, Transfer Matrix Method provides a fast and practical solution and, if compared to the FEM, the size of the system (the matrix) is smaller [84]. The TMM could be used in the determination both of thermal [85] and acoustic [86] performances. Recently, some studies approached the heat transfer problem using the Transfer Matrix Method [87], but at present, this methodology seems to be most appreciated and used in acoustics. In this latest field, TMM is applied to increase the simulation accuracy also in the low-frequency range using hybrid approaches that have been developed combining finite element method (FEM) or wave-based (WB) approaches with TMM model [86]. In the acoustic characterization, there are several models used

for the description of sound wave propagation which can be chosen basing on the morphology of the materials. For instance, in the case of woven fabrics it is possible to adopt the perfect plate [88] or the Attenborough model for fibrous materials, cellular foams or granular materials [89] or Miki model for fibrous materials and felt [90]. Anyway, recently, the Johnson-Champoux-Allard using Biot's theory is the widely used procedure to describe the visco-inertial dissipative effects inside the porous media [91] - [93]. Accordingly, Santoni et al. [94] highlight how the Transfer Matrix Method is more and more a diffused acoustic approach to sound transmission [95].

2.3 Selection of inherent papers

The research methodology is structured using inclusion and exclusion criteria and requirements. Firstly, the construction techniques and the structural elements are selected, with the aim to better focus on dedicated timber components production methodologies. To this aim, after an in-depth literature study, it is assessed that the most used ones [96] are Timber Frame (TF) and Cross Laminated Timber (CLT). Accordingly, these two methods are frequently presented, discussed and compared in literature both from thermal [97] and acoustic [98] point of views. Another inclusion criterion is to consider all the parameters needed to the simulation process.

In order to better focus on the needed input, the most used parameters on thermal and acoustic insulation simulation are introduced in the following. Accordingly, FEM, TMM and SEA often require the same input factors.

The thermal insulation model is mostly represented by the transmittance parameter, which is represented in Eq.1:

$$(1) \quad U = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{h_{cv,i}+h_{r,i}} + \frac{1}{h_{cv,e}+h_{r,e}} + \frac{d}{\lambda}}$$

where U is the thermal transmittance, $h_{cv,i}$ is the internal convective heat transfer coefficient, $h_{r,i}$ is the internal radiative heat transfer coefficient, $h_{cv,e}$ is the external convective heat transfer coefficient, $h_{r,e}$ is the external radiative heat transfer coefficient, λ is the material thermal conductivity and s is the thickness of the material. In case of more than one insulating layer, d/λ ratio has to be summed considering all the materials thicknesses and thermal conductivities.

The internal and external convective heat transfer coefficient depends on air movements around the vertical or horizontal walls. Usually, fix values are assumed for these parameters [99]. On the

other hand, radiative heat transfer coefficient are proportional to the emissivity of the material surfaces as expressed in eq. **Error! Reference source not found.:**

$$(2) \quad h_r = 4 \varepsilon \sigma T_m^3$$

where ε is the surface hemispherical emissivity, σ is the Stefan-Boltzmann coefficient and T is the mean thermodynamic temperature between the wall surface and its surroundings.

When analysing an insulating layer, heat transfer is mostly regulated by conductivity. Fourier's Law (Eq.3) describes this phenomenon:

$$(3) \quad q = -(\lambda_{\text{cond}} + \lambda_{\text{conv}} + \lambda_{\text{rad}}) \nabla T$$

where λ is the overall material thermal conductivity, q is conduction heat flux and ∇T is the gradient of temperature. When a material is taken into account in a dry condition, the equivalent thermal conductivity is depicted by a general equation (Eq. 4):

$$(4) \quad \lambda_e = f(\phi, \lambda_g, \lambda_f)$$

where λ_e is the material equivalent thermal conductivity, ϕ is the porosity, λ_g is the contained stagnant gas thermal conductivity, λ_s is the part thermal conductivity of the pore solid phase. Actually, in building constructions there will not be any gas motion inside thermal insulating layers. Thus, the stagnant air hypothesis is always considered valid. For this reason, the thermal conductivity value will be only described by a variation of porosity or tortuosity, using $\lambda_g = 0.02$ W/mK as a fixed value [100].

For the dynamic thermal performance of components, the periodic transmittance is considered. A Transfer Matrix has to be implemented to calculate this parameter, taking into account its main parameter, the periodic penetration depth δ , expressed by Eq.5:

$$(5) \quad \delta = \sqrt{\frac{\lambda T}{\pi \rho c}}$$

where T is the periodic variation, ρ is the density of the material and c is the specific heat capacity.

From the acoustic insulation point of view, the issue has to be divided into two topics:

- airborne transmission,

- structure borne transmission.

For the first case, for a frequency domain investigation, the well-established Johnson et al. [92] approach, modified by Champoux and Allard [93], is most of the time used to model or minimize the five factors influencing this phenomenon, namely:

- flow resistivity σ [N s m^{-4}],
- porosity ϕ [-],
- tortuosity α_{∞} [-],
- viscous characteristic length Λ [μm]
- thermal characteristic length Λ' [μm]

For the solid-borne sound propagation, the Hook's law relates a proportional dependence between stresses and strains. For isotropic elastic solids, it can be written in matrix form as (Eq. 6):

$$(6) \quad \sigma = C\varepsilon$$

where σ is the stress tensor applied to the elastic isotropic mean and ε is the obtained strain tensor. C is defined in Eq. 7 [101]:

$$(7) \quad C = \frac{E}{(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)} \begin{bmatrix} 1-\nu & \nu & \nu & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \nu & 1-\nu & \nu & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \nu & \nu & 1-\nu & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1-2\nu}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1-2\nu}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1-2\nu}{2} \end{bmatrix}$$

where E is the Young's Modulus and ν is the Poisson's ratio.

For the viscous-elastic case, a different elastic modulus value per frequency is assumed as well as for the Poisson's ratio. At the same time, for the damping effect, a complex E number is considered.

Thus, the complete list of necessary parameters for thermal [102], [103] and acoustic [104], [105], insulation numerical simulations is resumed in Table 1.

Table 1: List of the material properties necessary for the thermal and acoustic insulation simulations

<i>Mechanical parameters</i>		
density	ρ	[kg/m ³]
Young's modulus	E	[MPa]
Poisson's ratio	ν	[-]
<i>Thermal parameters</i>		
coefficient of emissivity	ε	[-]
thermal conductivity	λ	[W/(m K)]
specific heat at constant pressure	c_p	[J/(kg K)]
<i>Acoustic parameters</i>		
flow resistivity	σ	[(kPa s)/m ²]
porosity	ϕ	[%]
tortuosity	α_{∞}	[-]
viscous length	Λ	[μ m]
thermal length	Λ'	[μ m]

Thus, the listed parameters in Table 1 provides an additional inclusion criterion for the selection of papers.

To select the inherent works, the title, the results and the data mentioned have been screened to acquire an overview of potentially important material and outcomes of the research presented. After this process, the literature has been catalogued, which has been considered pertinent and providing the physical values researched. Consequently, only those data have been considered for this literature review analysis.

Conversely, excluding criteria were adopted, to better focus on this work topics. The criteria excluding papers are:

- the characterization of materials used in non-wooden building elements;
- the physical characterization of a material not belonging to neither of the two construction techniques above presented;

- the characterization of a physical parameter not included in the list defined in the previous section.

No excluding criteria have been adopted related to the year of publishing.

From the method depicted below, 42 papers were included to be discussed and compared.

2.4 Results and Discussion

2.4.1 Georeferenced and topics distribution

Basing on the approach depicted in Section 3, only a limited number of papers were included. Among these, three main topics were found: mechanical, thermal and acoustic characterization of the physical parameters. The topics distribution percentage of the sample is shown in Figure 15. Here, it is possible to understand that the mechanical and the thermal approach are the most diffused, while the acoustic characterization is the less discussed.

Percentage of topics treated by literature

Figure 15: Topics treated in the sample of papers collected.

Geographical origin distribution is reported in Figure 16, where on the left side, the continental division of the papers and research are depicted, on the right side, is displayed the country sorting. It can be noticed that the higher percentage comes from Europe, followed by North America, Asia and finally South America. From country sorting it can be seen that the most contributing countries are Italy (14%), China (10%) and both Romania and the United States (7%).

Figure 16: Geographic distribution of the papers collected - continental division (left) and nationality division (right)

2.4.2 Discussion of the literature results

The collection is related to the parameters listed in Table 1 for the simulation through the TMM and the FEM method, as described in Section 3. To better understand treated outcomes, this section will be divided on different sections. The analysis was performed analysing the single layers composing timber frame structure, while Cross Laminated Timber was treated as a whole, as it is not a multi-layered element.

For each material analysed a summary of the data found is depicted in a table by providing, if specified, the thickness of the material, the source providing the data and how the source found the information depicted. For the wooden materials, when possible, the type of wood was detailed.

2.4.2.1 Timber Frame

The analysis here proposed will be discussed in relation to mechanical, thermal and acoustic properties of each Timber Frame element.

Timber Stud

A synthetic summary about the timber stud physical characterization can be seen in Table 2. Many of the studies identified characterized timber stud mechanically with wide ranges of variability in density and Young Module. Conversely, no study, among those identified, dwells on the characterization of the Poisson ratio. As far as the thermal characterization of the timber stud is concerned, there are numerous data concerning the thermal conductivity and the specific heat at

constant pressure, but only two data concerning the emissivity. No study among those identified instead qualifies this material acoustically.

Table 2: summary of the parameters characterizing the Timber Stud

source	source of data provided	type of wood/stud	Thicknes	Mechanical parameters		Thermal parameters		
			s	ρ [kg/m ³]	E [MPa]	ε [-]	λ [W/(m K)]	cp [J/(kg K)]
			d [mm]					
[106]	data obtained from a variety of reports of research collected by the Authors	white oak	-		12270			
		red maple	-		11310			
		Douglas fir	-		13440			
		western white pine	-		10070			
		longleaf pine	-		13650			
		Laminated veneer lumber	-		8960-19240			
[107].	data obtained from laboratory tests performed by the Authors	Pine wood	-	340	10000			
[108]	data provided by the Delphin programme database + lab tests performed by Tampere University of Technology	Pine stud	50	532			0.11-0.13	
[109]	thermal conductivity provided by ISO 10456	Pine wood					0.16	
[110]	data from WUFI database	-	45	455			0.09	1500
[111]	data used by the Authors for simulation on BLOCON HEAT 2 based on ISO 10211	Spruce-pine-fir stud	-	455			0.1	1400
[112]	data adopted by the Authors for the performed computation; unknown data source	-	15	450			0.12	1500
			28					
[113]	Not specified	Oak wood	-	700			0.21	2090
		Spruce wood	-	500-600			0.14	
		Pine wood	-	500-600			0.14	
[114]	based on other studies cited by the Authors	-	-	400-700			0.08-0.15	
[115]	The database's source for each material listed is unknown and not provided	-	-				0.85	

[116]	The database's source for each material listed is not specified	-	-			0.82	
[117]	data from ONORM EN 12524 and ONORM B 8110-7	-	-	500			0.13

Oriented Strand Board (OSB)

A summary of the values regarding the OSB physical characterization is depicted in Table 3. As found for the timber stud, also the OSB is the focus of numerous studies that provided values on density and thermal conductivity. Unlike the previous material, however, only a few provided data of Young's modulus and specific heat at constant pressure. Then, in this case, only two studies furnished the Poisson's ratio, while from a thermal approach, data characterizing emissivity are missing. Also in this case, no studies were found that offer an acoustic characterization of the Oriented Strand Board.

Table 3: summary of the parameters characterizing the OSB

source	source of data provided	Thickness	Mechanical parameters			Thermal parameters	
		d [mm]	ρ [kg/m ³]	E [MPa]	ν [-]	λ [W/(m K)]	cp [J/(kg K)]
[106]	data obtained from a variety of reports of research collected by the Authors	-		4410-6280			
[107]	data obtained from laboratory tests performed by the Authors	-	550				
[108]	data provided by the Delphin program database + lab tests performed by Tamper University of Technology	50	646			0.11-0.13	
[109]	thermal conductivity provided by ISO 10456	-				0.13	
[110]	data from WUFI database	18	595			0.11	1700
[111]	data used by the Authors for simulation on BLOCON HEAT 2 based on ISO 10211	12	615			0.13	1400
[113]	data source not specified	-					
[118]	data obtained from laboratory tests performed by the Authors	14	606	3200	0.3		
		22					

[119]	average value detected by comparing several data provided by furnishers and product data sheets	-	600 -620				
[120]	data used for LCA evaluation, provided by product furnishers	8	520				
		12					
		25					
[121]	data obtained from laboratory tests performed by the Authors	14	700	3800	0.2		
		22					
[122]	data obtained from laboratory tests performed by the Authors	-	680			0.089	
[123]	average value measured by comparing the results of 5 samples	18	662			0.0959	
[124]	data provided by product furnishers	12	600			0.125	
[125]	data source not specified	9				0.13	
[126]	average value measured by comparing the results of 5 samples	-					1552

Insulation layer: Rock wool

Conversely to what found for OSB and timber stud, rockwool was characterized both from a thermal and acoustic perspective. For this reason, it was properly considered to examine in two different tables the studies characterizing the thermal and mechanical aspects (Table 4) and the acoustic and mechanical aspects (Table 5).

By analyzing the data collected on the mechanical characterization of rock wool is highlighted the great quantity of data regarding the density of this material, whereas Poisson ratio and Young's modulus are only provided by a study approaching the material acoustically. Then, focusing on the thermal characterization of the material (Table 4) there are many data provided for thermal conductivity, some for specific heat at constant pressure, but no data for emissivity.

Table 4: summary of the mechanical and thermal parameters characterizing the rock wool

source	source of data provided	Thickness	Mechanical parameters	Thermal parameters	
		d [mm]	ρ [kg/m ³]	λ [W/(m K)]	cp [J/(kg K)]

[108]	data provided by the Delphin programme database + lab tests performed by Tampere University of Technology	50		0.037	
[110]	data from WUFI database	160	60	0.04	850
[111]	data used by the Authors for simulation on BLOCON HEAT 2 based on ISO 10211	184	20	0.034	850
[113]	not specified	-	80-180	0.033-0.039	840
[115]	The database's source for each material listed is unknown and not provided	-	-	0.02-0.04	
[117]	data from ONORM EN 12524 and ONORM B 8110-7	-	15	0.040	
	data from ONORM EN 12524 and ONORM B 8110-7	-	30	0.042	
	based on other studies cited by the Authors	-	20-150	0.035-0.05	840
[119]	data source not specified	-	-	0.041	
[125]	thermal conductivity from ELMURST SAP ENERGY RATING software	-	23-45	0.033-0.040	
[127]	data source not specified	50	70		
[128]	data source not specified	-	70	0.035	
[129]	data provided by product furnishers	-	32	0.037	
[130]	based on other studies cited by the Authors	-	50-60	0.04	
[131]	based on other studies cited by the Authors	-	50-60	0.04	
[132]	data obtained by physical tests conducted in accordance with the National Research Council of Canada	76	96	0.032	850
[133]	The database's source for each material listed is unknown and not provided	-	20	0.032-0.044	1030
[134]	data source not specified	-	-	0.033-0.040	
[135]	data obtained from a variety of reports of research collected by the Authors	40	70		

As far as acoustics (Table 5 **Error! Reference source not found.**) are concerned, there is a lot of data for airflow resistivity, some values for porosity and tortuosity, but few values for thermal length and viscous length.

Table 5: summary of the mechanical and acoustic parameters characterizing the rock wool

source	source of data provided	Thickn ess	Mechanical parameters			Acoustic parameters				
		d [mm]	ρ [kg/m ³]	E [MPa]	ν [-]	σ [(kPa s)/m ²]	ϕ [%]	α_{∞} [-]	Λ [μ m]	Λ' [μ m]
[118]	The density of the material is provided by the furnishers, while other parameters were detected by lab tests	160	40			15.4	0.98	1.04	56	
[121]	the rockwool data are obtained by inversion from a Kundt tube measurement	160	40	0.014	0	14.08	0.99	1	76	137
[136]	data obtained from laboratory tests performed by the Authors	-	21			16.5	0.98	1.1		
[137]	data obtained from laboratory tests performed by the Authors	-	183			51.2	0.97	1.06		
[138]	data provided by product furnishers and flow resistivity measured by the Authors both for uncompressed and compressed material. For the rockwool different product were tested	140 (uc)				12 (uc)				
		100 (uc)				12 (uc)				
		100 (uc)				21 (uc)				
		100 (uc)				12 (uc)				
		100 (c)				18 (c)				
		75 (c)				21 (c)				
		75 (c)				30 (c)				
		75 (c)				20 (c)				

(uc) = data regarding the “uncompressed” sample;
(c) = data regarding the “compressed” sample

Insulation layer: Glass wool

The synthetic depiction of what found for the glass wool insulation characterization is depicted both in Table 6 for the thermal characterization and in Table 7 for the acoustical one.

From the analysis of the data collection, it is clear from the Table 6 that the thermal and mechanical studies lack values for Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio. On the other hand, the collected values provide ample values for the density of the material and its thermal conductivity but give few values for the specific heat at constant pressure and the emissivity of the material.

Table 6: summary of the mechanical and thermal parameters characterizing the glass wool

source	source of data provided	Thickness	Mechanical parameters	Thermal parameters		
		d [mm]	ρ [kg/m ³]	ε [-]	λ [W/(m K)]	cp [J/(kg K)]
[115]	the database's source for each material listed is unknown and not provided	-			0.023-0.040	
[107]	data obtained from laboratory tests performed by the Authors	-			0.05	
[113]	data source not specified	-	14-80		0.032-0.038	840
[117]	based on other studies cited by the Authors	-	25-220		0.035-0.05	840
[125]	thermal conductivity from ELMURST SAP ENERGY RATING software	-	(10-32)		0.033-0.040	
[130]	based on other studies cited by the Authors	-	34		0.034	
[135]	data obtained from a variety of reports of research collected by the Authors	-	30			
[139]	data obtained from a variety of reports of research collected by the Authors	-	18-50		0.04-0.05	
[140]	data source not specified	-			0.032-0.040	
[141]	thermal conductivity detected by hotbox according to Chinese GB/T13465-2008	89-140			0.042	
[142]	the database's source for each material listed is unknown and not provided	-		0.075		

Some of the studies that have acoustically approached glass wool have also provided data for the mechanical characterization of the material, as shown in Table 7. These provide few values for Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio, which were missing from the previous thermal analysis. As far as the acoustic parameters are concerned, the airflow resistivity is treated extensively, providing wide ranges. The other parameters of the JCA model are also depicted by some authors, but while for porosity and tortuosity the variation between the various studies is minimal, in the case of thermal length and viscous length the variations are more impressive.

Table 7: summary of the mechanical and acoustic parameters characterizing the glass wool

source	source of data provided	Thickness	Mechanical parameters			Acoustic parameters				
		d [mm]	ρ [kg/m ³]	E [MPa]	ν [-]	σ [(kPa s)/m ²]	ϕ [%]	α_{∞} [-]	Λ [μm]	Λ' [μm]
[118]	The density of the material is provided by the furnishers, while other parameters were detected by lab tests	80	56	0.6	0	36.23	0.99	1	40	162
[137]	data obtained from laboratory tests performed by the Authors	-	53			24.3	0.98	1.01	63	
[138]	data provided by product furnishers and flow resistivity measured by the Authors both for uncompressed and compressed material	50 (uc)				9 (uc)				
		32 (c)				12 (c)				
[143]	fixed data used for their evaluation; data source not specified	50	80			70				
[144]	evaluated with analytical process minimizing the error	25	17			14.2	0.99	1	182	400
[145]	fixed data used for their evaluation; data source not specified	45	16	0.055	0	15	0.98	1	60	150

(uc) = data regarding the "uncompressed" sample;

(c)= data regarding the "compressed" sample

Insulation layer: General Poro-elastic material

For the physical characterization of XPS (Extruded polystyrene) as expected, only thermal properties are provided by the several authors, as depicted in **Error! Reference source not found..** Although several values are given for the density and thermal conductivity of the XPS material there is a lack of data and characterization regarding certain mechanical properties (E , ν) and an acoustic representation of the material. In addition, the values provided by the many studies here proposed, contrary to what seen so far, are never related to the thickness of the insulation layer in the case of extruded polystyrene.

Table 8: summary of the parameters characterizing the XPS

source	source of data provided	Thickness	Mechanical parameters		Thermal parameters
		d [mm]	ρ [kg/m ³]	λ [W/(m K)]	cp [J/(kg K)]
[114]	based on other studies cited by the Authors	-	20-40	0.033	
[117]	based on other studies cited by the Authors	-	20-50	0.030-0.040	1500
[125]	thermal conductivity from ELMURST SAP ENERGY RATING software	-	≤400	0.027-0.036	
[133]	the database's source for each material listed is unknown and not provided	-	20-40	0.035	

Furthermore, for the Expanded Polystyrene (EPS) an extensive thermal analysis is offered by Table 9. This shows that the thermal conductivity of expanded polystyrene is almost always coupled with the density values and sometimes with information on the thickness of the insulation layer under consideration. Few data are available on the specific heat at constant pressure, while data on Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio are missing, as well as on the emissivity of EPS. An acoustic material characterization approach is also missing in this case.

Table 9: summary of the parameters characterizing the EPS

source	source of data provided	Thickness	Mechanical parameters		Thermal parameters
		d [mm]	ρ [kg/m ³]	λ [W/(m K)]	cp [J/(kg K)]
[111]	data used by the Authors for simulation on BLOCON HEAT 2 based on ISO 10211	151	25	0.034	1500

[112]	data adopted by the Authors for the performed computation; unknown data source	30	30	0.040	1500
		120			
[113]	data source not specified	-	20-60	0.03-0.04	900-1500
[117]	data from ONORM EN 12524 and ONORM B 8110-7	-	15.8	0.040	1500
	based on other studies cited by the Authors	-	15	0.035	
	based on other studies cited by the Authors	-	20	0.035	
	based on other studies cited by the Authors	-	30	0.040	
[130]	based on other studies cited by the Authors	-	30	0.031	
[131]	based on other studies cited by the Authors	-	30	0.031	
[134]	data source not specified	-	-	0.031-0.038	
[125]	thermal conductivity from ELMURST SAP ENERGY RATING software	-		0.032-0.040	

Few Authors also provided a thermal characterization of the foam glass (Table 10) providing some information on thermal conductivity, specific heat and density. As for the other pore-elastic materials analyzed in this subsection, data on young's modulus, Poisson's ratio, emissivity and the acoustic characterization approach of this material are missing.

Table 10: summary of the parameters characterizing the foam glass

source	source of data provided	Thickness	Mechanical parameters	Thermal parameters	
		d [mm]	ρ [kg/m ³]	λ [W/(m K)]	cp [J/(kg K)]
[113]	data source not specified	-	140	0.06	1100
[117]	based on other studies cited by the Authors	-	106-165	0.04-0.05	840
[125]	thermal conductivity from ELMURST SAP ENERGY RATING software	-		0.042	

Insulation layer: Natural Insulation material

Few Authors characterized also the natural insulation materials.

Of all the data collected, particular attention was given to sheep's wool, as shown in Table 11. A great deal of information was provided on the density of sheep's wool. Some studies have also provided data on thermal conductivity and only little information has been given on specific heat and airflow resistivity.

Table 11: summary of the parameters characterizing the foam glass

source	source of data provided	Thickness	Mechanical parameters	Mechanical parameters		Acoustic parameters
		d [mm]	ρ [kg/m ³]	λ [W/(m K)]	cp [J/(kg K)]	σ [(kPa s)/m ²]
[113]	data source not specified	-	20	0.04	900	
[130]	based on other studies cited by the Authors	-	30	0.04		
[131]	based on other studies cited by the Authors	-	30	0.04		
[135]	data obtained from a variety of reports of research collected by the Authors	-	100			
[146]	fixed data used for their evaluation; data source not specified	-	40			2.1

For the hemp physical characterization few data have been collected, as depicted in Table 12. As far as this natural insulation material is concerned, many authors have focused on its physical characterization. Of the several provided, there are many data regarding its acoustic description and density, few regarding its thermal conductivity, but there is a lack regarding its specific heat, emissivity, Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio.

Table 12: summary of the parameters characterizing the hemp

source	source of data provided	Thickness	Mechanical parameters	Thermal parameters	Acoustic parameters				
		d [mm]	ρ [kg/m ³]	λ [W/(m K)]	σ [(kPa s)/m ²]	ϕ [%]	α_{∞} [-]	Λ [μ m]	Λ' [μ m]

[130]	based on other studies cited by the Authors	-		0.04					
[139]	data obtained from a variety of reports of research collected by the Authors	-	20-45	0.04-0.06					
[144]	evaluated with analytical process minimizing the error	25	51		6.2	0.990	1.05		
[146]	fixed data used for their evaluation; data source not specified	-	50		1.4				
[147]	data are derived from averages calculated on at least three samples of each product	90	28.9		1.6	0.935	1	335	360
		90	24.1		3.3	0.976	1	359	453
		50	55.6		8.1	0.949	1.1	134	272
		8	91.8		11.0	0.936	1.4	58	122
		18	140.5		33.0	0.895	1.2	31	145
[148]	data from experimental and computational process depicted by the Authors	40	88		5.5	0.930	1.05	109	160

In the case of cellulose, too, numerous authors have dealt with the characterization of this insulation material, as can be seen from the Table 13. Although there are numerous data on density and thermal conductivity, few authors have provided data on specific heat at constant pressure and acoustic characterization. Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio, thermal emissivity of the material and thermal length are missing.

Table 13: summary of the parameters characterizing the cellulose

source	source of data provided	Thickness	Mechanical parameters	Thermal parameters		Acoustical parameters			
		d [mm]	ρ [kg/m ³]	λ [W/(m K)]	cp [J/(kg K)]	σ [(kPa s)/m ²]	ϕ [%]	α_{∞} [-]	Λ [μm]
[108]	data provided by the Delphin program database + lab tests performed by Tampere University of Technology	50	37 (dry cellulose)	0.048-0.049					
		50	60 (wet cellulose)	0.041-0.0043					
[110]	data from WUFI database	160	70	0.04	2500				
[113]	data source not specified	-	65,00	0.04	1800				

[115]	The database's source for each material listed is unknown and not provided	-		0.022-0.035					
[125]	thermal conductivity from ELMURST SAP ENERGY RATING software	-		0.038-0.044					
[130]	based on other studies cited by the Authors	-	35-70	0.037					
[139]	data obtained from a variety of reports of research collected by the Authors	-	30-45 (cellulose from recycled paper)	0.041					
		-	30-60 (cellulose from wood fibre)	0.050					
[149]	data used for computational investigation performed by the Authors on Foam Formed Cellulose	-	37.3		6	0.984	1.08	157.4	

Limited information was collected about the straw in **Error! Reference source not found.** From the Authors who provided data on the straw, only density, thermal conductivity and, in one case, airflow resistivity are provided. Information regarding its Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio, emissivity and all other parameters of the JCA acoustic model were not dealt.

Table 14: summary of the parameters characterizing the straw

source	source of data provided	Thickness	Mechanical parameters	Thermal parameters	Acoustic parameters
		d [mm]	ρ [kg/m ³]	λ [W/(m K)]	σ [(kPa s)/m ²]
[109]	thermal conductivity provided by ISO 10456	-		0.073	
[124]	provided by the product furnishers	50	79.43	0.054	
[140]	data source not specified	-		0.037	
[146]	fixed data used for their evaluation; data source not specified	-	50		1.4

Some authors have also approached wood fiber, as shown in the table. From the information collected, it is evident that most of the data reported by the Authors concern the density and thermal aspects (thermal conductivity and specific heat), leaving out most of the mechanical characterization (E , ν) and totally the acoustic characterization.

Table 15: summary of the parameters characterizing the wood fiber

source	source of data provided	Thickness	Mechanical parameters	Thermal parameters	
		d [mm]	ρ [kg/m ³]	λ [W/(m K)]	cp [J/(kg K)]
[108]	data provided by the Delphin program database + lab tests performed by Tamper University of Technology	50		0.048-0.050	
[110]	data from WUFI database	8;15	300	0.05	1500
[130]	based on other studies cited by the Authors	-		0.065	

Taban et al. [150] studied the sound absorption performance of date palm fibers and estimating some parameters varying the thickness of the insulation material. The results are summarized in No other Authors have provided a further characterisation of this specific material, providing the need for information on its mechanical and thermal characteristics and further investigation of its acoustic properties.

Table 16: summary of the parameters characterizing the date palm fiber

source	source of data provided	Thickness	Mechanical parameters	Acoustic parameters				
		d [mm]	ρ [kg/m ³]	σ [(kPa s)/m ²]	ϕ [%]	α_{∞} [-]	Λ [μ m]	Λ' [μ m]
[150].	data used for computational investigation performed by the Authors	20	65	1.07	0.9276	2.95	250	422
		30		0.956	0.9278	2.90	247	430
		40		0.879	0.9280	2.90	245	418

The cork has been characterized by Hairstans et al. [125] thermally and by Berardi and Iannace [146] acoustically. Details of their data are depicted in Table 17. As for the straw data regarding its Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio, emissivity and all other parameters of the JCA acoustic model were not dealt.

Table 17: summary of the parameters characterizing the cork

source	source of data provided	Thickness	Mechanical parameters	Thermal parameters	Acoustic parameters
		d [mm]	ρ [kg/m ³]	λ [W/(m K)]	σ [(kPa s)/m ²]
[125]	thermal conductivity from ELMURST SAP ENERGY RATING software	-	120	0.04-0.05	
[146]	fixed data used for their evaluation; data source not specified	-	100		1000

Few Authors also reported data for the coconut fibres as depicted in Table 18. The studies listed here report results mainly on density, Young's modulus, thermal conductivity, specific heat and the acoustic parameters of the JCA model. However, no values were found on Poisson's ratio and thermal emissivity.

Table 18: summary of the parameters characterizing the coconut fiber

source	source of data provided	Thickness	Mechanical parameters		Thermal parameters		Acoustical parameters				
		d [mm]	ρ [kg/m ³]	E [MPa]	λ [W/(m K)]	cp [J/(kg K)]	σ [(kPa s)/m ²]	ϕ [%]	α_{∞} [-]	Λ [μm]	Λ' [μm]
[107]	data obtained from laboratory tests performed by the Authors	-	1150-1460	4000-6000	0.04						
[113]	data source not specified	-	100		0.045	1600					
[130]	based on other studies cited by the Authors	-			0.043						

[146]	fixed data used for their evaluation; data source not specified	-	60				1.5				
[147]	data are derived from averages calculated on at least three samples of each product	105	101				11.581	0.945	1	68	339
[151].	data obtained from a variety of reports of research collected by the Authors	-	75-125		0.040-0.045						

The jute has been characterized by Fabbri et al.[151] thermally and by Gle et al. [147] acoustically. Data details are depicted in Table 19, but values about the main mechanical properties (E , ν), emissivity and specific heat are missing.

Table 19: summary of the parameters characterizing the jute

source	source of data provided	Thickness	Mechanical parameters	Thermal parameters	Acoustical parameters				
		d [mm]	ρ [kg/m ³]	λ [W/(m K)]	σ [(kPa s)/m ²]	ϕ [%]	α_{∞} [-]	Λ [μ m]	Λ' [μ m]
[147]	data are derived from averages calculated on at least three samples of each product	11	137.3		4.027	0.907	1	34	
[151]	data obtained from a variety of reports of research collected by the Authors	-	35-100	0.038-0.055					

Also for the kenaf Fabbri et al.[151] provided characterization thermically and Gle et al. [147] acoustically. The same considerations made previously can be done also for this material.

Table 20: summary of the parameters characterizing the kenaf

source	source of data provided	Thickness	Mechanical parameters	Thermal parameters	Acoustic parameters				
		d [mm]	ρ [kg/m ³]	λ [W/(m K)]	σ [(kPa s)/m ²]	ϕ [%]	α_{∞} [-]	Λ [μ m]	Λ' [μ m]
[147]	data are derived from averages calculated on at least three samples of each product	11	137.3		4.027	0.907	1	34	
[151].	data obtained from a variety of reports of research collected by the Authors	-	35-100	0.038-0.055					

Few considerations have also been made on the textile fibers. Firstly the cotton was thermally characterized bot from Asdrubali and Arenas [130] and Kymäläinen and Sjöberg [139], as shown in **Error! Reference source not found..**

Table 21: summary of the parameters characterizing the cotton

source	source of data provided	Thickness	Mechanical parameters	Thermal parameters
		d [mm]	ρ [kg/m ³]	λ [W/(m K)]
[130]	based on other studies cited by the Authors	-	25	0.04
[139]	data obtained from a variety of reports of research collected by the Authors	-	5-100	0.035-0.075

Secondly, also the flax was thermally characterized by some of the Authors previously introduced, details are depicted in Table 22**Error! Reference source not found..**

Table 22: summary of the parameters characterizing the flax

source	source of data provided	Thickness	Mechanical parameters	Thermal parameters
--------	-------------------------	-----------	-----------------------	--------------------

		d [mm]	ρ [kg/m ³]	λ [W/(m K)]	cp [J/(kg K)]
[113]	not specified	-	20	0.04	840
[135]	data obtained from a variety of reports of research collected by the Authors	-	40		

With regard to the previously mentioned textile fibre studies, it can be seen that acoustic characterization and information about Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio are strongly lacking.

Other Insulation material

Other materials have been characterized within the timber building framework. The polyurethane foam has been characterized by few Authors, how depicted in Table 23 **Error! Reference source not found.**, especially acoustically. Data about Young Modulus, Poisson's ratio and thermal properties are not provided.

Table 23: summary of the parameters characterizing the polyurethane foam

source	source of data provided	Thickness	Mechanical parameters	Acoustical parameters			
		d [mm]	ρ [kg/m ³]	σ [(kPa s)/m ²]	ϕ [%]	α_{∞} [-]	Λ [μ m]
[137]	data obtained from laboratory tests performed by the Authors	-	60	2.3	0.96	1.28	202
[143]	fixed data used for their evaluation; data source not specified	-	48				
[144]	evaluated with analytical process minimizing the error	-	25-55	5.4-12.9	0.97-1	1.08-1.41	

For the kraft, Pihelo and Kalamees [108] and Berardi and Iannace [146] provided some thermal data, especially thermal conductivity but, exception made for the density, all the mechanical and acoustical parameters were not detailed in no other studies here examined.

Table 24: summary of the parameters characterizing the kraft

source	source of data provided	Thickness	Mechanical parameters	Thermal properties
		d [mm]	ρ [kg/m ³]	λ [W/(m K)]
[108]	data provided by the Delphin program database + lab tests performed by Tampere University of Technology	-	756-900	0.11-0.12
[146]	fixed data used for their evaluation; data source not specified	-	400-470	0.85-1

2.4.3 Cross Laminated Timber

Contrary to the Timber Frame structure, the CLT is composed of the same wooden component layered in different directions, precisely each one oriented perpendicular to adjacent layers and glued on the wider faces of each board. Here, only a few papers among the one selected concern the characterization of CLT. The summary of these data is included in Table 25. From the data below described is highlighted the lack of acoustic characterization of Cross Laminated Timber and the lack of values about some mechanical properties (E , ν) and thermal emissivity.

Table 25: summary of the parameters characterizing the CLT

source	source of data provided	Thickness	Mechanical parameters	Thermal parameters	
		d [mm]	ρ [kg/m ³]	λ [W/(m K)]	cp [J/(kg K)]
[111]	data used by the Authors for simulation on BLOCON HEAT 2 based on ISO 10211, (spruce-pine-fir wood)	-	600	0.104	960
[112]	data adopted by the Authors for the performed computation; data source not specified	120;140	410	0.10	1300
[117]	data from ONORM EN 12524 and ONORM B 8110-7	-	500	0.13	
[119]	average value detected by comparing several data provided by furnishers and product data sheets	-	450		
[132]	data obtained by physical tests conducted in accordance with the National Research	102	536	0.12	2500

	Council of Canada, (Quebec black spruce wood)				
[152]	data provided by product furnishers, (spruce)	-	500	0.13	1600
[153]	data source not specified	-	470		
[154]	data provided by product furnishers	25	400		

2.5 Comments and Remarks

This research aims to provide a complete overview of the input parameters usable to simulate the performances of timber buildings elements. In order to fulfil this aim, some issues have to be solved in relation to construction methodologies, simulation approaches, materials characterizations and a consequent variability of the results. Thus, an in-depth literature review is developed and results are discussed in terms of distribution in time, bibliometric data cross-correlation, link between different research, simulation methodologies and analytic parameters involved in the calculations.

Many useful results can be here highlighted:

- ✓ The investigated topic is of great interest for the scientific community. Data show that in last one or two decades, we can find a rapidly increasing trend related to studies dealing with this thermal and acoustic insulation issues for timber buildings;
- ✓ Scientists do prefer conference proceedings instead of journal papers to disseminate their results. This is probably due to the fact that many funded projects do not pay for high open access fees, so it is simpler to present within international congresses;
- ✓ The most studied construction methodologies are Cross Laminated Timber and Timber Frame, even if a notable segmentation of research is assessed;
- ✓ Nowadays, computer simulations are not the most used methodology to study and predict timber buildings elements performances, probably because this approach need very robust and reliable materials characterization; it was also assessed a lack of this latter topic in literature;
- ✓ The most used simulation approaches are Finite Element Methods and Transfer Matrix Method, even if for acoustics also SEA is used;

From the point of view of parameters availability, all simulation methods are based on common factors. These were analysed, sorted and collected for all elements layers such as timber studs,

oriented strand board, insulation elements (such as rock, glass and sheep wool, hemp, cellulose, cork, cotton palm fibre, flax, kenaf, etc.) cross laminated timber. The results are resumed in table 2 where values of 11 parameters are reported for each considered layer. This constitutes the very first database containing input data for thermal and acoustic simulations of timber building elements. It has to be clearly specified that often studies report different values for similar materials, while sometimes it can be found that for very different materials very similar values are described. As a final conclusion we can clearly state that databases have to be considered only if real measurements are not available, nor possible. Accordingly, basing numerical simulation on literature values can be misleading, due to the wide presented ranges.

3 ACOUSTIC PERFORMANCE TESTING OF PARTITIONS

3.1 Introductions to the Laboratories

Within the framework of interregional collaboration and cooperation between the project partner universities, acoustic tests were carried out on similar resilient acoustic insulation materials in the two laboratories of the Free University of Bozen (IT) and University of Innsbruck – Universität Innsbruck (AT).

A description of the two facilities is hereby provided.

The University of Innsbruck laboratory consists of two coupled overlapping room aimed at determining the impact noise reduction and airborne sound insulation measurements on floor performance. It has been set up on the basis of a standard test stand (related to the dimensions). The special feature is that the flanking transmission can also be measured via the component connections.

The ceiling test stand for airborne and impact sound measurements has been set up based on a standardized test stand (related to the dimensions). It is also possible to measure the edge transmission via the component connections. The so built Laboratory test it is a mock-up not built according to the ISO requirements.

Figure 17: Ceiling test stand at the University of Innsbruck

The ceiling test stand consists of a transmitter room, a receiver room and a small measuring room. The transmitter room, the raw ceiling (separating component) and the upper part of the receiver room consist of cross laminated timber elements. The height of 1 m of the cross-laminated timber

element (upper part of the receiving room) is chosen in such a way that at least a quarter of the wavelength at 100 Hz can be absorbed. The lower part of the reception room consists of lime cement blocks and reinforced concrete with an areal mass of 500 kg/m² (corresponds to the standards for a sound test stand). For the installation of the decoupling bearing, the upper floor (broadcast room), with and without a ceiling element, can be raised up to 30 cm using hydraulic cylinders. An external staircase connects the measuring rooms.

Figure 18: Upper and lower part (left and middle), hydraulic cylinder to lift the floor (right)

As a special feature and important for this type of investigation, there is the option of applying pre-tension to the wall-ceiling-wall connection using fixed threaded rods. The level of preload can be adjusted using strain gauges mounted on the threaded rods. This makes it possible to simulate different loads (e.g. several floors) with regard to the effect of decoupling bearings.

Figure 19: Threaded rods for pre-tension applications

The noise test rooms (transmitter room, receiver room) have a floor area of 21.5 m² (5.24 m long; 4.10 m wide). The volume of the transmitter room is 53.0 m³ and that of the receiver room is 85.0

m³. For standard measurements, the 1 m high wooden frame can also be removed from the reception room, reducing the room volume to 63.5 m³. The cross-laminated timber ceiling used as a standard has a thickness of 160 mm. To replace the raw ceiling, the entire upper floor (broadcast room) can be lifted off with a truck-mounted crane. This construction of the sound test stand enables tests according to ÖNORM EN ISO 16283-1 and ÖNORM EN ISO 16283-2 to be carried out like construction site measurements.

In this way, practical results are achieved. In addition to the standard measurements for airborne and footfall noise, the secondary sound paths (flank transmission) can be measured with accelerometers. All sound measuring devices used in the test bench are calibrated according to the specifications of the measurement standards.

Figure 20: Two-storey test stand at the University of Innsbruck

The Free University of Bozen laboratory is composed of three coupled rooms: two for the measurement of airborne sound insulation of vertical components (partition walls), two overlapping rooms for the measurement of airborne and impact noise (ceilings/floor).

Figure 21. Three chamber set-ups at the Free University of Bozen

The laboratory was built in order to minimize flanking transmission according to ISO 10140–5 [155] in particular the two overlapped chambers are here characterized: the transmitting room (upstairs) has a volume of 50.9 m³ and the receiving room, downstairs, has a volume of 60.63 m³. The CLT floor consists of 5 cross layers covering a surface of 3000 mm × 4155 mm with an overall thickness of 200 mm and an overall density of 420 kg/m³. The solid wood slab elements consist of at least three and up to nine adjacent layers, which are arranged perpendicular to each other. With regard to the thickness of the solid wood slab element, thickness and orientation of individual layers are symmetrically assembled. The adhesive for bonding of the cross laminated timber and the finger joints of the individual boards is conform to EN 15425 -2017 [156]. The CLT floor (Figure 22), classified as a C24 according to the EN 338 – 2016 [157] and made of spruce wood. In addition, the laboratory is equipped with a mechanical crane that allows the lifting and positioning of a concrete slab in order to insert and easily change the resilient materials under test between the concrete slab and the CLT ceiling, as depicted in Figure 23.

Figure 22: CLT under examination from the receiving room (downstairs)

Figure 23: CLT floor coupled with concrete slab and insulating material

Therefore, joint measurements between the two universities were carried out firstly on the measurement of the performance of the impact materials, while the airborne sound insulation measurements for vertical partitions (walls) were only tested at the Free University of Bozen.

3.2 Acoustic characterization of partitions

In order to qualify the environment from an acoustic point of view, the ISO 10140 [158] - [161],[155] series of standards we referred to the following three parameters: the sound reduction index, the normalized impact sound pressure level and the impact force exposure level.

The sound reduction index, R , is a parameter used to measure airborne noise between a source and a receiving room. It is calculated using equation (1), in accordance with ISO 10140-2 [159]:

$$(1) \quad R = L_1 - L_2 + 10 \lg \frac{S}{A}$$

where L_1 is the energy-average sound pressure level in the source room, L_2 is the energy-average sound pressure level in the receiving room, S is the area of the partition (wall or floor), A is the equivalent absorption area in the receiving room.

The normalized impact sound pressure level is a measurement of impact noise typically used for measuring the performance of horizontal partitions. It is measured with a standard tapping machine and it is calculated using equation (2) according to ISO 10140-3 [160]:

$$(2) \quad L_n = L_i + 10 \lg \frac{A}{A_0}$$

where $A_0 = 10 \text{ m}^2$ is the reference equivalent absorption area.

Then, the standard impact noise generated by the tapping machine does not fit the real human walking noise or objects dropping. Therefore, the rubber ball is used, especially for lightweight partitions. Its use is robust and reliable and provides high repeatability [162]. The rubber ball generates this impact when it is dropped vertically from the height of 1 meter. The impact force exposure level, L_{FE} , produced by the rubber ball is reported in equation (3) [163]:

$$(3) \quad L_{FE} = 10 \lg \left[\frac{1}{T_{ref}} \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \frac{F^2(t)}{F_0^2} dt \right]$$

where $F(t)$ is the instantaneous force acted on the floor under test when the rubber ball is dropped on the floor, $F_0 = 1 \text{ N}$ is the reference force, $t_2 - t_1$ is the time duration of the impact force [s], $T_{ref} = 1 \text{ s}$ is the reference time interval. The energy-average maximum impact sound pressure level measured with the rubber ball, $L_{i,Fmax}$, is represented by the maximum sound pressure level using the “fast” time constant.

From the values measured in 1/3 octave bands it is possible to derive the single number indices R_w , $L_{n,w}$ and $L_{iA,Fmax}$ according to ISO 717-1 [164] and ISO 717-2 standard [165]. R_w and $L_{n,w}$ are evaluated in the frequency range 100 Hz – 5000 Hz, while $L_{iA,Fmax}$ is the A-weighted sound pressure level evaluated in the frequency range 50 Hz – 630 Hz.

3.3 Results on insulating materials for floors

3.3.1 Results of the parallel measurements at the Free University of Bozen and at the University of Innsbruck.

Among the several materials tested at both universities as part of the project, one was tested in both laboratories, showing a good performance in both scenarios. The thickness of the tested material is of 28 mm, consisting mainly of polyurethane.

Test results will be discussed with reference to the measurement of the raw ceiling of each laboratory, showing variations and similarities in different test environments under the same standardized acoustic stress.

With reference on the sound reduction index measured in the two test cases, some consideration can be made. How showed by the results depicted in Figure 24 it is possible to understand how the performance of the two floors at medium low frequencies are similar, with regard to airborne noise insulation in both laboratories. Indeed, the Free University of Bozen (blue) trend and the University of Innsbruck (yellow) until 1600 Hz are quite similar, while at high frequencies if there is a decline for the yellow trend, this is not the case for the blue trend. As can be deduced naturally, the differences are due to the different nature of construction of the two laboratories.

With regard to the resilient insulation material analyzed (green trend in both cases), it can be seen that the performance of the material is higher in both cases. In particular, it can be seen that in the application of the Bolzano Laboratory, the material performs almost uniformly for all frequency ranges, having optimal performance in the high-medium frequencies. In the case study of the Innsbruck Laboratory, the material performs well in the medium frequencies, following a decrease in the high frequencies due to the intrinsic nature of the laboratory under investigation. Nevertheless, the material performs well in both case studies, showing an average good performance in airborne noise insulation.

Figure 24: Sound reduction index

Focusing now on the results produced for the measurement of the normalized impact sound pressure level through the use of a standard tapping machine some preliminary observations must be made. Looking at the results in Figure 25, it can immediately be seen that the trends of the raw floors in consideration (blue trend on the left and yellow trend on the right) are quite different. The substantial difference is the difference in the concrete slab used in the two cases. In the Free University of Bozen, the slab is presented as a single pre-consolidated surface which is laid on top of the resilient material by means of a mechanical winch allowing the easy interchange of the materials in question. In the case of the laboratory floor at the University of Innsbruck, the slab is made up of several pre-consolidated concrete blocks to represent the in-situ realization slab. These blocks are laid next to each other after laying the resilient material under investigation. The two technologies under consideration are a valuable though different representation of the reality of installation. Nevertheless, with the addition of the resilient impact-insulating material, the behavior was uniform and the performance of the material in both laboratories was actually good, showing that the impact noise produced by the tapping machine was well dampened.

Figure 25: Normalized impact sound pressure level

With reference to the impacting force resulting from the rubber ball stress (Figure 26), it can be observed in the case of the rough slab in the Laboratory of the University of Innsbruck (Figure 26 -left, yellow trend) similar behavior to the one seen for the stress with the standard tapping machine (Figure 25 – right), once more related to the discontinuous blocks forming the concrete slab. Once again, but with less effect than in the previous case, the insulating material attenuates the discontinuity, but performs less effectively on the low-frequency stress produced by the rubber ball in the behavior depicted in the right side of Figure 26. On the other hand, very high-performance results are presented in the same test performed at the Laboratory of the Free University of Bozen (left side trends - Figure 26).

Figure 26: Impact sound pressure level (rubber ball)

3.4 Results on insulating materials for floors

This section will present some results of the many tests on several resilient impact-insulating materials acoustic performed at the laboratories of the Free University of Bozen. The results will be shown in groups for each material supplier showing, as done in the previous section, the results on air insulation, impact insulation by both standard tapping machine and rubber ball.

3.4.1 First group

The first group of materials to be examined in this section is composed as follows:

- 1 – red: Expanded polyethylene with Ethylene Vinyl Acetate closed cell, thickness 10 mm, density 35 kg/m³.
- 2- yellow: Expanded polyethylene, density 35 kg/m³, with 8 mm thick reflective aluminized protective film.
- 3 – green: Recycled rubber, thickness 3 mm, density 720 kg/m³, with a felt in recycled fibers, mass per unit area 0.6 kg/m², thickness 4 mm.
- 4 -blue: Expanded polyethylene with Ethylene Vinyl Acetate additive, thickness 4 mm, density 25 kg/m³ with an elastomeric layer, thickness 2 mm, mass per unit area 2 kg/m².
- 5 – purple: Double layer of natural and synthetic fibers heat-bound together, thickness 8 mm, mass per unit area 0.6 kg/m², with protective film.

Looking at the results of the sound reduction index depicted in Figure 27 it is possible to highlight how among all the five materials the n.5 -purple (double layer of natural and synthetic fibers heat-bound together) is the one performing better in this configuration both at low and high frequencies, followed by n.3 -green (recycled rubber with a felt in recycled fibers) and n.4 -blue (expanded polyethylene with Ethylene Vinyl Acetate additive and an elastomeric layer) characterised by having very similar behaviour despite their different composition. Material n. 1- red (expanded polyethylene with Ethylene Vinyl Acetate closed cell) also shows good performance in insulating against airborne noise, especially at low to medium frequencies.

Figure 27: First group – Sound reduction index

Then, looking at the results of the normalized sound pressure levels produced by the standard tapping machine (Figure 28) some considerations can be made. Among the five materials the n.5 – purple shows the best performance insulating the impact noise, especially in the range of low and medium frequencies that are the most concerning the impact noise. This is followed, more or less equally, by the performances of materials n.1 - red, n.2 -yellow and n.3-green. This latest material, made of recycled rubber with a felt in recycled fibers, shows an impressive high-frequency performance. Conversely the blue trend – n.4 (expandend polyethylene with Ethylene Vinyl Acetate additive and an elastomeric layer) seems to be the less performing in this configuration.

Figure 28: First group - Normalized impact sound pressure level

Looking to the results produced by the impact force of the rubber ball (Figure 29) it is possible to see that also for this type of solicitation, as already seen for the impact noise produced by the standard tapping machine, the material with highest performance is the n.5 – purple (double layer of natural and synthetic fibers heat-bound together) and the less performant is the material n.4 – blue (expanded polyethylene with Ethylene Vinyl Acetate additive and an elastomeric layer).

Figure 29: First group - Impact sound pressure level (rubber ball)

3.4.2 Second group

The first group of materials to be examined in this section is composed as follows:

1 – red: Ethylene-Propylene Diene Monomer rubber granules anchored with carboxylate latex binder to a backing, made with 80 g/m² non-woven film and 200 g/m² polyester fibre. Total thickness 10 mm, mass per unit area 2.65 kg/m².

2 – yellow: Fibres and granules of SBR rubber, selected and compacted using a polyurethane glue. Total thickness 5 mm, mass per unit area 3.70 kg/m².

3 – green: Panels, made of a 8 mm thick SBR rubber granules hot pressed with polyurethane binder, density 800 kg/m³ and a 20 mm thick polyester fiber panel, density 100 kg/m³. Total thickness 28 mm, mass per unit area 10.0 kg/m².

4 – blue: Panels made of two rubber bearings inserted in a polyester fiber mat, density 40 kg/m³. Bearings made of SBR and Ethylene-Propylene Diene Monomer rubber granules and fibers compacted using polyurethane glue, protected with a non-woven, non-stretch, synthetic membrane on one side; the dimensions of the rubber bearings are 300 mm x 50 mm. Total thickness 30 mm, mass per unit area 1,90 kg/m².

Results of the sound pressure index in Figure 30 shows that the material with the best performance for the airborne insulation is the n.3 – green (Panels, made of SBR rubber granules hot pressed with polyurethane binder and a polyester fiber panel). The other materials show a lower performance by not standing out individually, although material no. 2 – yellow (fibres and granules of SBR rubber, selected and compacted using a polyurethane glue), seems to isolate airborne noise the least in this case.

Figure 30: Second group – Sound reduction index

Confirming what already observed for airborne sound insulation, material No. 3 -green seems to be the one with the best performance also in impact noise insulation, as shown in Figure 31, followed by material no.4 - blue and finally by material no.1 - red. Material No.2 - yellow appears to be the least performing for this insulation as well.

Figure 31: Second group - Normalized impact sound pressure level

The results produced by the rubber impact ball stress analysis, shown in Figure 32, show very similar results to those analysed in both airborne and impact noise insulation produced by the standard tapping machine. In fact, in general, material no. 3 - green performs best, while material no. 1 - red performs surprisingly well at very low frequencies (50-80 Hz).

Figure 32: Second group - Impact sound pressure level (rubber ball)

3.4.3 Third group

The third group of materials under analysis is described below:

- 1 – red: Synthetic latex of centrifuged rubber with a wavy surface.
- 2 – yellow: Panel composed of fabrics of cotton, linen and wool filaments, with polypropylene glue. Polyethylene film pre-glued on one side.
- 3 – green: Closed cell expanded polyethylene. Thickness 5 mm.
- 4 – blue: Closed cell expanded polyethylene. Thickness 9 mm.

Figure 33 shows results on sound reduction index. Looking to the overview of the results, the materials no.1 – red and no.2 – yellow seems to be the best performing, showing a similar trend in insulation against airborne noise. On the contrary, material No. 4 - blue shows poor performance and the one with the lowest insulation seems to be No. 3 - green.

Figure 33: Third group – Sound reduction index

The results of the impact noise insulation produced by the standard tapping machine (Figure 34) show performance partially similar to that of the airborne noise insulation. Indeed, material no. 1 - red performs most effectively at low to medium frequencies, while material no. 2 - yellow performs best at medium to high frequencies. Confirming them as the best performing materials in this group. The least performing material for this type of analysis is material no. 4 - blue.

Figure 34: Third group - Normalized impact sound pressure level

In this case, the results of the rubber impact ball (Figure 35) show how, at very low frequencies, the behaviour of the four materials differs from what was analysed for the other two indices, showing that material no. 4 - blue is the one that performs best in the 50 - 80 Hz range. In spite of this, material no. 1 - red in this case is the best performer overall when looking at the entire frequency range under analysis.

Figure 35: Third group - Impact sound pressure level (rubber ball)

3.4.4 Fourth group

The fourth group of insulating materials tested is composed as follows:

1 – red: Mineralized fir wood wool, 3 mm wide, bound with grey Portland cement. Thickness 20 mm, density 500 kg/m³.

2 – blue: Mineralized fir wood wool, 3 mm wide, bound with grey Portland cement. Thickness 15 mm, density 533 kg/m³.

In this particular case, where the materials vary not in composition, but only in density and thickness, it can be seen that the variations in performance are generally very similar. Particularly, looking at the results of the sound reduction index in Figure 36, it can be observed how often trends overlap and do not perform significantly better than the other. Nevertheless, it can be seen that

material no. 1 – red (Thickness 20 mm, density 500 kg/m³) of the two seems to be more effective especially in the frequency ranges 100 - 315 Hz and 500 - 1250 Hz, while in the remaining ranges material no. 2 – blue (Thickness 15 mm, density 533 kg/m³) performs better.

Figure 36: Fourth group – Sound reduction index

As mentioned in the analysis of airborne noise insulation, the behaviour of the two materials is also extremely similar for the normalized impact sound pressure levels (Figure 37), especially from 400 Hz upwards. At low frequencies, on the other hand, the thicker and lower density material (material no. 1 - red) appears to be more effective.

Figure 37: Fourth group - Normalized impact sound pressure level

Differently from the noise produced by the standard tapping machine, in the case of the impact noise produced by the rubber ball (Figure 38) the trends of the two materials overlap up to 200 Hz, showing practically identical performance. For frequencies higher than 200 Hz, however, the material with the higher density and lower thickness (no. 2 - blue) performs slightly better.

Figure 38: Fourth group - Impact sound pressure level (rubber ball)

3.5 Results on insulating materials for walls

This section will present the results obtained testing several insulating materials for airborne noise performed at the laboratories of the Free University of Bozen. The results will be depicted, as done in the previous section, comparing the results of airborne insulation with the bare solution in each group. The bare wall is a timber frame element composed of studs (60x140 mm, 600 mm spacing) coupled with mineral wool (140 mm, 70 kg/m³) and OSB (15 mm, 550 kg/m³).

3.5.1 First group

The first group of materials to be examined in this section is composed as follows:

1 – red: Timber frame wall: timber studs (60x140 mm, 600 mm spacing), mineral wool (140 mm, 70 kg/m³), OSB (15 mm, 550 kg/m³). 1 gypsum board (12.5 mm, 720 kg/m³) screwed to the OSB in the source room.

2- yellow: Timber frame wall: timber studs (60x140 mm, 600 mm spacing), mineral wool (140 mm, 70 kg/m³), OSB (15 mm, 550 kg/m³). 1 gypsum board (12.5 mm, 720 kg/m³) screwed to the OSB in the source and in the receiving room.

3 – green: Timber frame wall: timber studs (60x140 mm, 600 mm spacing), mineral wool (140 mm, 70 kg/m³), OSB (15 mm, 550 kg/m³). 2 gypsum boards (2x12.5 mm, 720 kg/m³) screwed to the OSB in the source and in the receiving room.

4 – blue: Timber frame wall: timber studs (60x140 mm, 600 mm spacing), mineral wool (140 mm, 70 kg/m³), OSB (15 mm, 550 kg/m³). 2 gypsum boards (2x12.5 mm, 720 kg/m³) screwed to the OSB in the source room.

Results on the airborne insulation of the 4 insulation layers included in this group are depicted in Figure 39. Measurements shows how the wall n.3 – green (timber studs coupled with mineral wool, OSB and 2 gypsum boards screwed to the OSB in the source and in the receiving room) is the one performing better both at low and high frequencies. The second best-performing wall appears to be wall no.2-yellow (timber studs coupled with mineral wool, OSB and 1 gypsum board screwed to the OSB in the source and in the receiving room) up to medium frequencies (>250 Hz), while at low frequencies the second best-performing is wall no.4-blue (timber studs coupled with mineral wool, OSB and 2 gypsum screwed to the OSB in the source room) in the 50-250 Hz range.

Figure 39: First group - walls: Sound reduction index

3.5.2 Second group

The second group of materials to be examined in this section is composed as follows:

1 – red: Timber frame wall: timber studs (60x140 mm, 600 mm spacing), mineral wool (140 mm, 70 kg/m³), OSB (15 mm, 550 kg/m³). Timber studs (40x60 mm, 600 mm spacing), mineral wool (40 mm, 38 kg/m³), 1 gypsum board (12.5 mm, 720 kg/m³) in the source room.

2- yellow: Timber frame wall: timber studs (60x140 mm, 600 mm spacing), mineral wool (140 mm, 70 kg/m³), OSB (15 mm, 550 kg/m³). Timber studs (40x60 mm, 600 mm spacing), mineral wool (40 mm, 38 kg/m³), 1 gypsum board (12.5 mm, 720 kg/m³) in the source and in the receiving room.

3 – green: Timber frame wall: timber studs (60x140 mm, 600 mm spacing), mineral wool (140 mm, 70 kg/m³), OSB (15 mm, 550 kg/m³). Timber studs (40x60 mm, 600 mm spacing), mineral wool (40 mm, 38 kg/m³), 2 gypsum boards (2x12.5 mm, 720 kg/m³) in the source and in the receiving room.

4 – blue: Timber frame wall: timber studs (60x140 mm, 600 mm spacing), mineral wool (140 mm, 70 kg/m³), OSB (15 mm, 550 kg/m³). Timber studs (40x60 mm, 600 mm

spacing), mineral wool (40 mm, 38 kg/m³), 2 gypsum boards (2x12.5 mm, 720 kg/m³) in the source room.

Results on the airborne insulation of the 4 insulation layers included in this group are depicted in Figure 40. Also in this group, the measurements show how the wall n.3 – green is the one performing better both at medium and high frequencies, while at very low frequencies (50-63 HZ) the n.4 -blue wall seems to have better performances. The wall n.2- yellow is a wall that performs well especially in the frequency range 250-5000 HZ, while wall no. 1- red, seems among the four of the second group to be the least performing among the overall frequencies range.

Figure 40:Second group - walls: Sound reduction index

3.5.3 Third group

The second group of materials to be examined in this section is composed as follows:

1 – red: Timber frame wall: timber studs (60x140 mm, 600 mm spacing), mineral wool (140 mm, 70 kg/m³), OSB (15 mm, 550 kg/m³). 10 mm airgap, C-profiles (50 mm), mineral wool (40 mm, 38 kg/m³), 2 gypsum boards (2x12.5 mm, 720 kg/m³) in the source room.

2- yellow: Timber frame wall: timber studs (60x140 mm, 600 mm spacing), mineral wool (140 mm, 70 kg/m³), OSB (15 mm, 550 kg/m³). 10 mm airgap, C-profiles (50 mm),

mineral wool (40 mm, 38 kg/m³), 2 gypsum boards (2x12.5 mm, 720 kg/m³) in the source and in the receiving room.

3 – green: Timber frame wall: timber studs (60x140 mm, 600 mm spacing), mineral wool (140 mm, 70 kg/m³), OSB (15 mm, 550 kg/m³). 10 mm airgap, C-profiles (50 mm), mineral wool (40 mm, 38 kg/m³), 1 gypsum board (12.5 mm, 720 kg/m³) in the source and in the receiving room.

4 – blue: Timber frame wall: timber studs (60x140 mm, 600 mm spacing), mineral wool (140 mm, 70 kg/m³), OSB (15 mm, 550 kg/m³). 10 mm airgap, C-profiles (50 mm), mineral wool (40 mm, 38 kg/m³), 1 gypsum board (12.5 mm, 720 kg/m³) in the source room.

Results on the airborne insulation of the 4 insulation layers included in this group are depicted in Figure 41. In this group measurements shows how the wall n.2 – yellow is the one performing better both at very low and high frequencies (50-2500 HZ) showing the best overall performance. Immediately after follows the n.3 – green wall particularly at medium – high frequencies (125-2500 HZ), while at very low frequencies (50-125 Hz) and very high frequencies (2500-5000 Hz) the n.1 – red wall it seems to be one of the best in this group for airborne insulation. The n.4 -blue wall conversely is the least performing in the third group.

Figure 41: Third group - walls: Sound reduction index

4 THERMAL SIMULATION ON INDOOR COMFORT

In order to study how well the materials in this analysis perform with the national and international standards of the regions involved in the Interreg area, a thermal comfort analysis was carried out and simulated using the *"Therm"* software. This analysis, in addition to understanding whether the minimum requirements for each country involved in the BIGWOOD project are met, also explores the indoor performance with the *"EnergyPlus"* simulation tool of a building designed according to both the Project Partner CasaClima standards and the BIGWOOD proposal expressed in the planning tool including the national and regional standards and requirements for Italy and Austria.

4.1 Preliminary consideration on simulation

This study is aimed at assessing whether the thermal performance of buildings with wood-based façades is equivalent to that of buildings made with more massive materials, typically used in buildings, such as clay block. In particular, it is intended to analyze if the lower thermal inertia and the lower thickness of this type of building envelopes has a negative impact on the indoor thermal comfort conditions or on the energy consumption of the HVAC systems.

Figure 42: Perspective of the standard open office space.

For this purpose, multiple dynamic thermal simulations of an intermediate floor of a standard open office building (Figure 42) have been carried out, comparing the thermal performance of two types

of wood enclosures (timber-frame and cross laminated timber) with the reference building made with a higher thermal mass material (clay block). Different variants of each building construction are simulated, according to the requirements of the following standards and certification systems: Austria (OIB-6), Italy (DM 26.06.2015, Climate Zone F), CasaClima and Bigwood (M 3.1, Defined Quality Requirements). These requisites and construction systems are compared in four cities (Figure 43) within the area of the INTERREG project: Innsbruck, Bozen, Vicenza and Udine.

Figure 43: Area of the Italy-Austria Interreg Project

The simulated space is based on a simplified shoebox-like geometry, with a volume of 300 m³, a square floor surface of 100 m², and a window of 9 x 1.5 m (45% WWR) oriented to the North (Figure 42). The north orientation was chosen to avoid the use of both fixed and occupant-operated solar shading devices, which would introduce more complexity and variability to the simulations. Table 26 summarizes the main building simulation settings.

Table 26: Building simulation settings.

Simulation Settings	Value
Floor area	100 m ²
Height	3 m
Window Area	13.5 m ² (9 m x 1.5 m)
Occupancy Period	Monday to Friday
Occupancy Hours	8 am to 6 pm
Heating Setpoint Time	Heating: 6 am to 6 pm;
Cooling Setpoint Time	Cooling: 7 am to 6 pm
Occupancy Density [166]	0.12 people m ⁻²

Occupants Activity	1.2 met
Vapor production rate	0.05 kg h ⁻¹ per person
Ventilation Rate [166]	Occupied: 1.58 ACH; Unoccupied: 0.05 ACH
Internal Gains [167]	Occupied: 20 W m ⁻² ; Unoccupied: 2 W m ⁻²
Heating Setpoint	Winter: 20 °C; Summer: 23 °C
Cooling Setpoint	Winter: 24°C; Summer: 26 °C
Setback Temperatures	Heating: 15 °C; Cooling: 28 °C
Humidity Control	Not available

4.2 Description of materials to meet the minimum requirements for each standard

In the following paragraphs, there will be specified the constructions of the external walls used in the simulations. The walls were design to fulfill the minimum requirements of the regulations/certification systems by adding or removing insulation material in increments of 1 cm.

4.2.1 AUSTRIA

According to the Austrian regulations, the U-value of the external walls of a new building must be less than or equal to 0.35 W/m2K. The composition of the walls used in this study are as follows:

- **Reference Building**

Plaster (0.7 cm) – Glass Wool (9 cm) – Clay Block (20 cm) → U-Value = 0.347 W/m2K

- **Timber framed Building**

OSB (1.4 cm) + Mineral Wool (11 cm) / Beam (11 cm) + OSB (2.2 cm) → U-Value = 0.334 W/m2K. The U-Value of this configuration was calculated with the software *Therm* to account for the thermal bridges of the wooden beams (Figure 44).

Figure 44: Wood construction that fulfills the minimum requirements of the Austrian OIB-6 regulation.

- **Cross-laminated Building**

Plaster (0.7 cm) – Glass Wool (8 cm) – X-Lam (10 cm) → U-Value = 0.323 W/m2K

4.2.2 CASACLIMA

According to the CasaClima certification system, the U-value of the external walls of a new building must be less than or equal to 0.33 W/m²K. The composition of the walls used in this study are as follows:

- **Reference Building**

Plaster (0.7 cm) – Glass Wool (10 cm) – Clay Block (20 cm) → U-Value = 0.318 W/m²K

- **Timber framed Building**

OSB (1.4 cm) + Mineral Wool (12 cm) / Beam (12 cm) + OSB (2.2 cm) → U-Value = 0.334 W/m²K. The U-Value of this configuration was calculated with the software *Therm* to account for the thermal bridges of the wooden beams, as depicted in Figure 45.

Figure 45: Wood construction that fulfills the minimum requirements of the CasaClima certification system.

- **Cross-laminated Building**

Plaster (0.7 cm) – Glass Wool (8 cm) – X-Lam (10 cm) → U-Value = 0.323 W/m²K

4.2.3 ITALY

According to the Italian regulations for the climatic zone F, the U-value of the external walls of a new building must be less than or equal to 0.24 W/m²K. The composition of the walls used in this study are as follows:

- **Reference Building**

Plaster (0.7 cm) – Glass Wool (14 cm) – Clay Block (20 cm) → U-Value = 0.238 W/m²K

- **Timber framed Building**

OSB (2.2 cm) + Mineral Wool (16 cm) / Beam (16 cm) + OSB (2.2 cm) → U-Value = 0.239 W/m²K. The U-Value of this configuration was calculated with the software *Therm* to account for the thermal bridges of the wooden beams (Figure 46).

Figure 46: Wood construction that fulfills the minimum requirements of the Italian DM 26.06.2015 regulation for the climate zone F.

- **Cross-laminated Building**

Plaster (0.7 cm) – Glass Wool (13 cm) – X-Lam (10 cm) → U-Value = 0.226 W/m²K

4.2.4 BIGWOOD PROPOSAL

According to the proposals made in M 3.1, defined quality requirements, the U-value of the external walls of a new building must be less than or equal to 0.15 W/m²K. The composition of the walls used in this study are as follows:

- **Reference Building**

Plaster (0.7 cm) – Glass Wool (24 cm) – Clay Block (20 cm) → U-Value = 0.146 W/m²K

- **Timber framed Building**

Plaster (0.7 cm) – Glass Wool (10 cm) – OSB (1.4 cm) + Mineral Wool (16 cm) / Beam (16 cm) + OSB (2.2 cm) → U-Value = 0.145 W/m²K. The U-Value of this configuration was calculated with the software *Therm* to account for the thermal bridges of the wooden beams (Figure 47).

Figure 47: Wood construction that fulfills the minimum requirements of proposal of the Bigwood project.

- **Cross-laminated Building**

Plaster (0.7 cm) – Glass Wool (22 cm) – X-Lam (10 cm) → U-Value = 0.147 W/m²K

4.3 Energy consumption simulation

In this section there will be discussed the energy consumption results, performed with EnergyPlus, of the four cities case studies (Bolzano, Udine, Vicenza, Innsbruck) looking is difference subsists among the four regulation and standards here discussed and if there are differences in energy consumption between a traditional massive building (reference building) and timber one.

Analyzing the results obtained for the Bolzano site (Figure 48), it can be seen that in almost all four cases, the energy consumption of a traditional building constructed from solid elements (reference building) and that of a building constructed from cross laminated timber are extremely similar. As for the timber framed building, its consumption is higher than the other two types by only one kW/year in each standard requirement here discussed. The BIGWOOD requirements results to be for the Bozen site the less energy consuming allowing savings of 1 to 3 kW/year compared to the other minimum requirements under analysis.

Figure 48: Energy consumption estimation for the 4 different requirements - Bozen site

Looking to the results of the simulation results it can be observed that for Udine (Figure 51) the reference building has always an energy consumption equal or higher than the two timber building, with the exception of the BIGWOOD suggestion where consumption is lower than all the other standards and the difference between the three building types adopting this type of minimum requirements is almost none.

Figure 49: Energy consumption estimation for the 4 different requirements - Udine site

Also in the case of Vicenza, the timber building (both Timber Framed and Cross Laminated) are less demanding from an energy saving perspective for all four minimum or standard requirements under analysis (Figure 50). Again, the BIGWOOD suggestion would save up to 2Kw/year in the energy consumption balance of both a timber building and a building made of massive materials.

Figure 50: Energy consumption estimation for the 4 different requirements - Vicenza site

Looking instead at the simulated energy consumption results on the Innsbruck site in Figure 51, it can be seen that the three configurations are rather equivalent and in many cases the energy demand of the two timber configurations is slightly lower than that of a conventional building, demonstrating an equal energy efficiency in this case as well.

Figure 51: Energy consumption estimation for the 4 different requirements - Innsbruck site

4.4 Indoor Comfort simulation

In particular, this section analyses the variation of the thermal comfort expressed by the variation of Prediction Mean Vote (PMV) index evaluated during the occupational time in an office building according to the description provided in the Section 4.1. The PMV was simulated by the simulation performed on EnergyPlus and calculated according to ASHRAE 55 and ISO 7730.

Results of the four cities investigated (Bozen, Udine, Vicenza, Innsbruck) were simulated for the three different types of building and for the four types of minimum requirements/standards investigated in this work (Austria OIB-6, Italy DM 26.06.2015, CasaClima and Bigwood suggestion). Results are depicted in Figure 52- Figure 55 and expressed through a “Cumulative duration plot” that express the indoor comfort condition during the occupancy time of the office building, thus taking into account exclusively the working hours.

The results and trends clearly shows firstly how the indoor comfort condition are similar among the different conditions of the typologies of buildings, of the several minimum requirements and analyzed for the 4 sites here studied. Secondly, it can be observed how the variation of PMV is lower than 0.2 for less than the half of occupancy time for all the cases taken into account (3 types of building, 4 types of minimum requirements, 4 cities). This latest shows once again how adopting timber as a construction material, both for a timber framed building or for a cross laminated building, does not impact on the indoor condition granted by the minimum requirement of each region involved in the Interregional Italy- Austria Project.

Figure 52: PMV Cumulative duration Plot - Bolzano

Figure 53: PMV Cumulative duration Plot - Udine

Figure 54: PMV Cumulative duration Plot - Vicenza

Figure 55: PMV Cumulative duration Plot - Innsbruck

4.5 Remarks and comments

The results of the simulations show that despite the variation in construction technology (massive construction material of the reference building, Timber framed building and Cross laminated building) the variations in energy consumption in the 2 locations of the Interreg territory are minimal (as shown in the dedicated paragraph). The same can be observed for simulations and evaluations of indoor comfort, showing how the adoption of a timber solution in the Interregional territory Italy Austria does not vary the comfort guaranteed to the user by the building.

5 CONCLUSION

From the numerous results analysed and discussed in the report, numerous observations can be made regarding both the bibliographic research conducted and the body of knowledge to which the BIGWOOD project contributes, but also regarding the results of the tests conducted in the laboratories of the universities participating in the project:

- the extensive literature search conducted made it possible to highlight which topics the research within this project should emphasise and study more;
- the numerous acoustic measurements on both vertical and horizontal partitions, in the latter case tested in both laboratories involved in the project, show that there are numerous insulations on the market that can guarantee good performance for timber buildings;
- the thermo-hygrometric wellbeing simulation carried out by the Free University of Bozen/Bolzano shows that at different locations within the involved Interreg area IT-AT, the comfort conditions enhanced to the occupants by timber buildings are still guaranteed if they are built to the suggested standards (WP3 – deliverable: planning tool including the national and regional standards and requirements for Italy and Austria). Moreover, buildings constructed in this way are energy-efficient as guaranteed by the highest accreditors, thus fully demonstrating the potential of timber buildings.

6 References

- [1] M. Zhen, B. Zhang, Energy Performance of a Light Wood-Timber Structured House in the Severely Cold Region of China, *Sustainability*. 10 (2018) 1501. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10051501>.
- [2] A. Stocchero, J.K. Seadon, R. Falshaw, M. Edwards, Urban Equilibrium for sustainable cities and the contribution of timber buildings to balance urban carbon emissions: A New Zealand case study, *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 143 (2017) 1001–1010. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.12.020>.
- [3] J. Tollefson, The wooden skyscrapers that could help to cool the planet, *Nature News*. 545 (2017) 280.
- [4] M. Ramage, H. Burrige, M. Wicher, G. Fereday, T. Reynolds, D. Shah, G. Wu, L. Yu, P. Fleming, D. Densley Tingley, J. Allwood, P. Dupree, P.F. Linden, O. Scherman, The wood from the trees: The use of timber in construction, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*. 68 (2017) 333–359. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.09.107>.
- [5] T. Goverse, M.P. Hekkert, P. Groenewegen, E. Worrell, R.E.H.M. Smits, Wood innovation in the residential construction sector; opportunities and constraints, *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*. 34 (2001) 53–74. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0921-3449\(01\)00093-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0921-3449(01)00093-3).
- [6] F. Werner, K. Richter, Wooden building products in comparative LCA, *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*. 12 (2007) 470–479. <https://doi.org/10.1065/lca2007.04.317>.
- [7] M. Asif, Sustainability of timber, wood and bamboo in construction, in: *Sustainability of Construction Materials*, 2007. <https://doi.org/10.1533/9781845695842.31>.
- [8] K. Sandler, Analyzing what's recyclable in C&D debris, *BioCycle*. 44 (2003) 51–59.
- [9] J. Lyslo Skullestad, R.A. Bohne, J. Lohne, High-rise Timber Buildings as a Climate Change Mitigation Measure – A Comparative LCA of Structural System Alternatives, *Energy Procedia*. 96 (2016) 112–123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2016.09.112>.
- [10] V.A. De Araujo, et al., Classification of Wooden Housing Building Systems, *BioResources*. 11 (2016) 7889–7901. <https://doi.org/10.15376/biores.11.3.DeAraujo>.
- [11] E. COM, Roadmap to a resource efficient Europe, Communication from the Commission to European Parliament, the Council, the European Social and Economic Committee and the Committee of the Regions. Brussels: European Commission. (2011).
- [12] A. Toppinen, A. Röhr, S. Pätäri, K. Lähinen, R. Toivonen, The future of wooden multistory construction in the forestbioeconomy – A Delphi study from Finland and Sweden, *Journal of Forest Economics*. 31 (2018) 3–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfe.2017.05.001>.
- [13] B. Xia, T. O'Neill, J. Zuo, M. Skitmore, Q. Chen, Perceived obstacles to multi-storey timber-frame construction: an Australian study, *Architectural Science Review*. 57 (2014) 169–176. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00038628.2014.912198>.
- [14] A. Hafner, S. Schäfer, Environmental aspects of material efficiency versus carbon storage in timber buildings, *Journal of Wood and Wood Products*. 76 (2018) 1045–1059. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00107-017-1273-9>.
- [15] L. Pajek, B. Hudobivnik, R. Kunič, M. Košir, Improving thermal response of lightweight timber building envelopes during cooling season in three European locations, *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 156 (2017) 939–952. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.04.098>.
- [16] J.W.G. Van De Kuilen, A. Ceccotti, Z. Xia, M. He, Very tall wooden buildings with cross laminated timber, *Procedia Engineering*. 14 (2011) 1621–1628.
- [17] H. Dahlbo, J. Bachér, K. Lähinen, T. Jouttijärvi, P. Suoheimo, T. Mattila, S. Sironen, T. Myllymaa, K. Saramäki, Construction and demolition waste management – a holistic evaluation of environmental performance, *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 107 (2015) 333–341. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2015.02.073>.

- [18] M.K. Kuzman, D. Sandberg, Comparison of timber-house technologies and initiatives supporting use of timber in Slovenia and in Sweden - the state of the art, *IForest - Biogeosciences and Forestry*. (2017) 930–938. <https://doi.org/10.3832/ifor2397-010>.
- [19] K. Lähtinen, C. Harju, A. Toppinen, Consumers' perceptions on the properties of wood affecting their willingness to live in and prejudices against houses made of timber, *Wood Material Science & Engineering*. 14 (2019) 325–331. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17480272.2019.1615548>.
- [20] Z. Hu, J. Zhang, Z. Deng, Construction process simulation and safety analysis based on building information model and 4D technology, *Tsinghua Science and Technology*. 13 (2008) 266–272.
- [21] S. AbouRizk, Role of simulation in construction engineering and management, *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*. 136 (2010) 1140–1153.
- [22] G. Mustafaraj, D. Marini, A. Costa, M. Keane, Model calibration for building energy efficiency simulation, *Applied Energy*. 130 (2014) 72–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2014.05.019>.
- [23] J.L.M. Hensen, R. Lamberts, Introduction to building performance simulation, in: *Building Performance Simulation for Design and Operation*, Taylor & Francis Group, n.d.
- [24] H. Wang, Z. (John) Zhaib, Advances in building simulation and computational techniques: A review between 1987 and 2014, *Energy and Buildings*. 128 (2018) 319–335. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2016.06.080>.
- [25] L. Kucerova, M. Cernikova, B. Hrubá, Thermal properties of wooden buildings in relation to computer software, *Advanced Materials Research*. 899 (2014) 193–196. <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMR.899.193>.
- [26] P. Lallemand, L.-S. Luo, Theory of the lattice Boltzmann method: Acoustic and thermal properties in two and three dimensions, *Physical Review E*. 68 (2003) 036706.
- [27] P. Ricciardi, E. Belloni, F. Cotana, Innovative panels with recycled materials: thermal and acoustic performance and life cycle assessment, *Applied Energy*. 134 (2014) 150–162.
- [28] X. Yu, Q. Zhang, J. Kang, F. Cui, Predicting integrated thermal and acoustic performance in naturally ventilated high-rise buildings using CFD and FEM simulation, in: *Building Simulation*, Springer, 2018: pp. 507–518.
- [29] M. Morsy, M. Fahmy, H.A. Elshakour, A.M. Belal, Effect of thermal insulation on building thermal comfort and energy consumption in Egypt, *Journal of Advanced Research in Applied Mechanics*. 43 (2018) 8–19.
- [30] J.M. Navarro, J. Escolano, Simulation of building indoor acoustics using an acoustic diffusion equation model, *Journal of Building Performance Simulation*. 8 (2015) 3–14.
- [31] M.R. Hall, S.P. Casey, D.L. Loveday, M. Gillott, Analysis of UK domestic building retrofit scenarios based on the E.ON Retrofit Research House using energetic hygrothermics simulation – Energy efficiency, indoor air quality, occupant comfort, and mould growth potential, *Building and Environment*. 70 (2013) 48–59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2013.08.015>.
- [32] I. Skotnicová, Z. Galda, P. Tymova, L. Lausova, Experimental Measurements and Numerical Simulations of Dynamic Thermal Performance of External Timber Frame Wall, *Advanced Materials Research*. 899 (2014) 126–130. <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMR.899.126>.
- [33] H.M. Cho, J.H. Park, S. Wi, S.J. Chang, G.Y. Yun, S. Kim, Energy retrofit analysis of cross-laminated timber residential buildings in Seoul, Korea: Insights from a case study of packages, *Energy and Buildings*. 202 (2019) 109329. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2019.07.046>.
- [34] L. Aye, T. Ngo, R.H. Crawford, R. Gammampila, P. Mendis, Life cycle greenhouse gas emissions and energy analysis of prefabricated reusable building modules, *Energy and Buildings*. 47 (2012) 159–168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2011.11.049>.
- [35] A. Doodoo, L. Gustavsson, R. Sathre, Lifecycle primary energy analysis of low-energy timber building systems for multi-storey residential buildings, *Energy and Buildings*. 81 (2014) 84–97. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2014.06.003>.

- [36] A. Batard, T. Duforestel, L. Flandin, B. Yrieix, Prediction method of the long-term thermal performance of Vacuum Insulation Panels installed in building thermal insulation applications, *Energy and Buildings*. 178 (2018) 1–10.
- [37] A. Korjenic, V. Petránek, J. Zach, J. Hroudová, Development and performance evaluation of natural thermal-insulation materials composed of renewable resources, *Energy and Buildings*. 43 (2011) 2518–2523.
- [38] X. Jin, M.A. Medina, X. Zhang, On the importance of the location of PCMs in building walls for enhanced thermal performance, *Applied Energy*. 106 (2013) 72–78.
- [39] M. Caniato, Sound insulation of complex façades: A complete study combining different numerical approaches, *Applied Acoustics*. 169 (2020) 107484.
- [40] V. Hongisto, D. Oliva, J. Keränen, Subjective and objective rating of airborne sound insulation–living sounds, *Acta Acustica United with Acustica*. 100 (2014) 848–863.
- [41] G. Ciaburro, G. Iannace, Numerical Simulation for the Sound Absorption Properties of Ceramic Resonators, *Fibers*. 8 (2020) 77.
- [42] R. Zulkifli, M.M. Nor, M.M. Tahir, A.R. Ismail, M.Z. Nuawi, Acoustic properties of multi-layer coir fibres sound absorption panel, *Journal of Applied Sciences*. 8 (2008) 3709–3714.
- [43] G. Fratoni, D. D’Orazio, L. Barbaresi, Acoustic comfort in a worship space made of cross-laminated timber, *Building Acoustics*. 26 (2019) 121–138.
- [44] Interact, Keep.eu, (n.d.). <https://keep.eu/> (accessed July 19, 2020).
- [45] European Commission, Research and Innovation, European Commission. (n.d.). https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation_en (accessed July 19, 2020).
- [46] FormaWood, (2014). <https://www.formawood.eu/> (accessed June 24, 2020).
- [47] FormaWood, (n.d.). 2017 FormaWood (accessed June 24, 2020).
- [48] NERO, NERO: Wood for Zero. (2017). <https://neroproject.net/> (accessed June 24, 2020).
- [49] Build-in-Wood, (2019). <https://www.build-in-wood.eu/> (accessed June 24, 2020).
- [50] D. Poole, A.E. Raftery, Inference for deterministic simulation models: the Bayesian melding approach, *Journal of the American Statistical Association*. 95 (2000) 1244–1255.
- [51] S. Malinov, W. Sha, Software products for modelling and simulation in materials science, *Computational Materials Science*. 28 (2003) 179–198.
- [52] J.M. Magallanes, Importance of concrete material characterization and modelling to predicting the response of structures to shock and impact loading, *Structures under Shock and Impact X*. 98 (2008) 241–250.
- [53] R. Schacht, D. May, B. Wunderle, O. Wittler, A. Gollhardt, B. Michel, H. Reichl, Characterization of thermal interface materials to support thermal simulation, *ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:0709.1849*. (2007).
- [54] Y. Zheng, R.G. Maev, I.Y. Solodov, Review/sythèse nonlinear acoustic applications for material characterization: a review, *Canadian Journal of Physics*. 77 (2000) 927–967.
- [55] European Committee on Standardization, Eurocode 8: Design of structures for earthquake resistance – Part 1: General rules, seismic actions and rules for buildings -EN 1998-1, (2004).
- [56] M. Li, F. Lam, R.O. Foschi, S. Nakajima, T. Nakagawa, Seismic performance of post and beam timber buildings I: model development and verification, *Journal of Wood Science*. 58 (2012) 20–30. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10086-011-1219-5>.
- [57] A. Palermo, S. Pampanin, M. Fragiaco, A. Buchanan, B. Deam, Innovative seismic solutions for multi-storey LVL timber buildings, in: 2006.
- [58] M. Popovski, J. Lindt, Analytical study on seismic force modification factors for cross-laminated timber buildings, *Canadian Journal of Civil Engineering*. 40 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.1139/cjce-2013-0021>.
- [59] G. Rinaldin, M. Fragiaco, Non-linear simulation of shaking-table tests on 3- and 7-storey X-Lam timber buildings, *Engineering Structures*. 113 (2016) 133–148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2016.01.055>.

- [60] Z. Li, M. He, Z. Ma, K. Wang, R. Ma, In-Plane Behavior of Timber-Steel Hybrid Floor Diaphragms: Experimental Testing and Numerical Simulation, *Journal of Structural Engineering*. 142 (2016) 04016119. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)ST.1943-541X.0001601](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)ST.1943-541X.0001601).
- [61] C. Loss, T. Tannert, S. Tesfamariam, State-of-the-art review of displacement-based seismic design of timber buildings, *Construction and Building Materials*. 191 (2018) 481–497. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2018.09.205>.
- [62] A. Ceccotti, C. Sandhaas, A proposal for a standard procedure to establish the seismic behaviour factor q of timber buildings, 11th World Conference on Timber Engineering 2010, WCTE 2010. 4 (2010).
- [63] S. Ormarsson, M. Johansson, Finite element simulation of global structural behaviour of multifamily timber buildings using prefabricated volume modules, in: 2018.
- [64] Y. Sui, J. Chang, H. Ye, Numerical Simulation of Semi-Rigid Element in Timber Structure Based on Finite Element Method, in: Y. Yuan, J. Cui, H.A. Mang (Eds.), *Computational Structural Engineering*, Springer Netherlands, Dordrecht, 2009: pp. 643–652.
- [65] Y. Xiao, J. Ma, Fire simulation test and analysis of laminated bamboo frame building, *Construction and Building Materials*. 34 (2012) 257–266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2012.02.077>.
- [66] J. Schmid, M. Klippel, A. Just, A. Frangi, M. Tiso, Simulation of the Fire Resistance of Cross-laminated Timber (CLT), *Fire Technology*. 54 (2018) 1113–1148. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10694-018-0728-9>.
- [67] J. Björkman, E. Mikkola, Risk assessment of a timber frame building by using CRISP simulation, *Fire and Materials*. 25 (2001) 185–192. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fam.770>.
- [68] M. Fontana, A. Frangi, Fire safety of multistory timber buildings, *Proceedings of The Institution of Civil Engineers-Structures and Buildings - PROC INST CIVIL ENG-STRUCT B*. 163 (2010) 213–226. <https://doi.org/10.1680/stbu.2010.163.4.213>.
- [69] N. Werther, J.W. O’Neill, P.M. Spellman, A.K. Abu, P.J. Moss, A.H. Buchanan, S. Winter, Parametric study of modelling structural timber in fire with different software packages, (2012).
- [70] N.J. Van Eck, L. Waltman, V.O.S Viewer Manual, Version 1 .6.15, 2020.
- [71] B. Kiss, C.G. Manchón, L. Neij, The role of policy instruments in supporting the development of mineral wool insulation in Germany, Sweden and the United Kingdom, *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 48 (2013) 187–199.
- [72] X. Zhang, X. Hu, H. Gong, J. Zhang, Z. Lv, W. Hong, Experimental study on the impact sound insulation of cross laminated timber and timber-concrete composite floors, *Applied Acoustics*. 161 (2020) 107173.
- [73] Q. Chen, Q. Fei, Y. Li, S. Wu, P. Zhang, Prediction of statistical energy analysis parameters in thermal environment, *Journal of Spacecraft and Rockets*. 56 (2019) 687–694.
- [74] K. Gawecka, D.M.G. Taborda, D. Potts, E. Sailer, W. Cui, L. Zdravkovic, Finite-Element Modeling of Heat Transfer in Ground Source Energy Systems with Heat Exchanger Pipes, *International Journal of Geomechanics*. (2020). [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)GM.1943-5622.0001658](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)GM.1943-5622.0001658).
- [75] J.-M. Bergheau, R. Fortunier, Finite Element Simulation of Heat Transfer, 2008. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470611418.part1>.
- [76] V. Pukhkal, A.B. Mottaeva, FEM modeling of external walls made of autoclaved aerated concrete blocks, *Magazine of Civil Engineering*. 81 (2018) 202–211. <https://doi.org/10.18720/MCE.81.20>.
- [77] R. Pirk, C. Góes, W. Desmet, P. Sas, FEM/FEM versus FEM/BEM vibro-acoustic coupling techniques applied to the Brazilian Vehicle Satellite Launcher (VLS) fairing problem: advantages and drawbacks, 2005.
- [78] S. ISHIDA, H. MORIMURA, Y. GOTOU, I. HAGIWARA, A new method to compute sound transmission loss by acoustic FEM, *Transactions of the JSME (in Japanese)*. 80 (2014) DR0127–DR0127. <https://doi.org/10.1299/transjsme.2014dr0127>.

- [79] H.Y. Kim, J.H. Jeon, Y.J. Kang, H.S. Choi, Sound Transmission Loss Prediction of a Wiring Grommet by Using the FEM, in: INTER-NOISE and NOISE-CON Congress and Conference Proceedings, Institute of Noise Control Engineering, 2019: pp. 4801–4810.
- [80] A. Tadeu, I. Simões, N. Simões, J. Prata, Simulation of dynamic linear thermal bridges using a boundary element method model in the frequency domain, *Energy and Buildings*. 43 (2011) 3685–3695.
- [81] Y. Ji, S. Chen, W. Zhu, The effect of pore numbers in the cell walls of soybean oil polyurethane foam on sound absorption performance, *Applied Acoustics*. 157 (2020) 107010.
- [82] S. Marburg, Six boundary elements per wavelength: Is that enough?, *Journal of Computational Acoustics*. 10 (2002) 25–51.
- [83] J. Zhang, S. Chauhan, Fast explicit dynamics finite element algorithm for transient heat transfer, *International Journal of Thermal Sciences*. 139 (2019) 160–175. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijthermalsci.2019.01.030>.
- [84] K. Bozdogan, F. Khosravi Maleki, AN APPLICATION OF THE MODIFIED FINITE ELEMENT TRANSFER MATRIX METHOD FOR A HEAT TRANSFER PROBLEM, *Kırklareli Üniversitesi Mühendislik ve Fen Bilimleri Dergisi*. (2019). <https://doi.org/10.34186/klujes.564004>.
- [85] X. Hou, Z. Deng, G. Yin, Application of transfer matrix method in heat transfer performance analysis of multi-re-entrant honeycomb structures, *Heat and Mass Transfer*. 50 (2014) 1765–1782. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00231-014-1352-y>.
- [86] A. Santoni, P. Fausti, P. Bonfiglio, Building materials: Influence of physical, mechanical and acoustic properties in sound prediction models, *Building Acoustics*. 26 (2018) 3–20. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1351010X18795403>.
- [87] S. Fan, J.R. Barber, Solution of periodic heating problems by the transfer matrix method, *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*. 45 (2002) 1155–1158. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0017-9310\(01\)00216-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0017-9310(01)00216-2).
- [88] L. Jaouen, F.-X. Bécot, Acoustical characterization of perforated facings, *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*. 129 (2011) 1400–1406.
- [89] K. Attenborough, Acoustical characteristics of rigid fibrous absorbents and granular materials, *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*. 73 (1983) 785–799.
- [90] Y. Miki, Acoustical properties of porous materials-generalizations of empirical models, *Journal of the Acoustical Society of Japan (E)*. 11 (1990) 25–28.
- [91] K. Verdière, R. Panneton, S. Elkoun, T. Dupont, P. Leclaire, Transfer matrix method applied to the parallel assembly of sound absorbing materials, *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*. 134 (2013) 4648–4658.
- [92] D.L. Johnson, J. Koplik, R. Dashen, Theory of dynamic permeability and tortuosity in fluid-saturated porous media, *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*. 176 (1987) 379–402. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022112087000727>.
- [93] Y. Champoux, J. Allard, Dynamic tortuosity and bulk modulus in air-saturated porous media, *Journal of Applied Physics*. 70 (1991) 1975–1979. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.349482>.
- [94] A. Santoni, J. Davy, P. Fausti, P. Bonfiglio, A review of the different approaches to predict the sound transmission loss of building partitions, *Building Acoustics*. (2020) 1351010X2091159. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1351010X20911599>.
- [95] K. Kesour, L. Alimonti, N. Atalla, Comments on the validity of transfer matrix based models for the prediction of the effect of curved sound packages, *Journal of Sound and Vibration*. 465 (2020) 114990. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsv.2019.114990>.
- [96] T. Reynolds, D. Casagrande, R. Tomasi, Comparison of multi-storey cross-laminated timber and timber frame buildings by in situ modal analysis, *Construction and Building Materials*. 102 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2015.09.056>.
- [97] L. Setter, E. Smoorenburg, S. Wijesuriya, P.C. Tabares-Velasco, Energy and hygrothermal performance of cross laminated timber single-family homes subjected to constant and variable

- electric rates, *Journal of Building Engineering*. 25 (2019) 100784.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2019.100784>.
- [98] D.P. Hindman, M.V. Golden, Acoustical Properties of Southern Pine Cross-Laminated Timber Panels, *Journal of Architectural Engineering*. 26 (2020) 05020004.
- [99] I. ISO, ISO 6946: 2017 Building Components and Building Elements—Thermal Resistance and Thermal Transmittance—Calculation Methods, International Organization for Standardization: Geneva, Switzerland. (2017).
- [100] G.W. Todd, Thermal conductivity of air and other gases, *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A, Containing Papers of a Mathematical and Physical Character*. 83 (1909) 19–39.
- [101] J. Allard, N. Atalla, *Propagation of sound in porous media: modelling sound absorbing materials 2e*, John Wiley & Sons, 2009.
- [102] R. Luo, W. Wu, W. Mortel, A Method to Predict the Heat Generation in a Rubber Spring Used in the Railway Industry, *Proceedings of The Institution of Mechanical Engineers Part F-Journal of Rail and Rapid Transit - PROC INST MECH ENG F-J RAIL R*. 219 (2005) 239–244.
<https://doi.org/10.1243/095440905X8862>.
- [103] O. MASAT, HEAT TRANSFER MODELING AND SIMULATION, (2017).
- [104] P. Zvolenský, J. Grecik, L. Kašiar, V. Stuchly, Simulation of sound transmission through the porous material, determining the parameters of acoustic absorption and sound reduction, *MATEC Web of Conferences*. 157 (2018) 02058. <https://doi.org/10.1051/mateconf/201815702058>.
- [105] F. Løvholt, K. Norèn-Cosgriff, C. Madshus, S.E. Ellingsen, Simulating low frequency sound transmission through walls and windows by a two-way coupled fluid structure interaction model, *Journal of Sound and Vibration*. 396 (2017) 203–216. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsv.2017.02.026>.
- [106] Z. Cai, R.J. Ross, Mechanical Properties of Wood-Based Composite Materials, in: *Wood Handbook : Wood as an Engineering Material: Chapter 12*, Madison, WI : U.S. Dept. of Agriculture, Forest Service, Forest Products Laboratory, 2010: p. 12.1-12.12.
- [107] K. Villa, C. Echavarría, D. Blessent, Wood walls insulated with coconut fiber, *Revista DYNA*. 86 (2019) 333–337. <https://doi.org/10.15446/dyna.v86n210.73685>.
- [108] P. Pihelo, T. Kalamees, The effect of thermal transmittance of building envelope and material selection of wind barrier on moisture safety of timber frame exterior wall, *Journal of Building Engineering*. 6 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2016.02.002>.
- [109] P. Brzyski, M. Grudzińska, D. Majerek, Analysis of the Occurrence of Thermal Bridges in Several Variants of Connections of the Wall and the Ground Floor in Construction Technology with the Use of a Hemp–Lime Composite, *Materials*. 12 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma12152392>.
- [110] C. Coupillie, M. Steemana, N. Van Den Bosschea, K. Maroy, Evaluating the hygrothermal performance of prefabricated timber frame façade elements used in building renovation, in: Elsevier Ltd., Trondheim, Norway, 2017: pp. 933–938. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2017.09.727>.
- [111] S.J. Chang, S. Wi, S. Kim, Thermal bridging analysis of connections in cross-laminated timber buildings based on ISO 10211, *Construction and Building Materials*. 213 (2019) 709–722.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2019.04.009>.
- [112] F. Fedorik, A. Haapala, Impact of Air-gap Design to Hygro-thermal Properties and Mould Growth Risk Between Concrete Foundation and CLT Frame, in: Elsevier Ltd., Trondheim, Norway, 2017: pp. 117–122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2017.09.656>.
- [113] C. Brischke, M. Humar, S. Thelandersson, Function: Bio-based materials for structural purposes, in: *Performance of Bio-Based Building Materials*, Elsevier Ltd., 2017.
- [114] H.M. Kunzel, *Simultaneous Heat and Moisture Transport in Building Components: one and two dimensional calculation using simple parameters.*, 1995.
- [115] Nuclear Power: Insulation Materials – Types of Insulation, <https://www.nuclear-power.net/> (n.d.). <https://www.nuclear-power.net/nuclear-engineering/heat-transfer/heat-losses/insulation-materials/>.
- [116] MIKRON, Table of emissivity of various surfaces, (n.d.).

- [117] M. Teibinger, I. Matzinger, Construction with Cross-laminated Timber in Multi-storey Buildings: Focus on Building Physics: Guidelines, Holzforschung Austria, 2013.
- [118] M. Caniato, F. Bettarello, P. Bonfiglio, A. Gasparella, Extensive investigation of multiphysics approaches in simulation of complex periodic structures, Applied Acoustics. 166 (2020) 107356.
- [119] B. Ingelaere, CHAPTER 4 ACOUSTIC DESIGN OF LIGHTWEIGHT TIMBER FRAME CONSTRUCTIONS, in: Action FP0702: Forests, Their Products and Services, n.d.
- [120] V.V. Ribeiro, A.P. Dassi-Leite, E.C. Pereira, A.D.N. Santos, P. Martins, R. de Alencar Irineu, Effect of Wearing a Face Mask on Vocal Self-Perception during a Pandemic, Journal of Voice. (2020).
- [121] M. Caniato, P. Bonfiglio, F. Bettarello, A. Gasparella, Innovative Approach in Acoustic Simulation of Timber Walls, in: 16th IBPSA International Conference and Exhibition, Rome, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.26868/25222708.2019.211114>.
- [122] Kamkee, Zylkowski, Effect of wood-based panel characteristics on thermal conductivity, For Prod J. 52 (1989) 75–83.
- [123] W. Sonderegger, P. Niemz, Thermal conductivity and water vapour transmission properties of wood-based materials., Eur. J. Wood Prod. 67 (2009) 313–321. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00107-008-0304-y>.
- [124] S.-V. Georgescu, C. Cosereanu, A. Fotin, L.-M. Brenci, L. Costiuc, Experimental thermal characterization of timber frame exterior wall using reed straws as heat insulation materials, Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry. 138 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10973-019-08325-2>.
- [125] R. Hairstans, R. Dodyk, A. Kermani, Sustainable Timber Frame Diaphragm Development, in: Glasgow, 2007.
- [126] Ł. Czajkowski, W. Olek, J. Weres, R. Guzenda, Thermal properties of wood based panels: specific heat determination, Wood Sci Technol. 50 (2016) 537–545. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00226-016-0803-7>.
- [127] E.A. Piana, N. Granzotto, A. Di Bella, A. Speranza, Sound transmission loss of cross-laminated timber walls: Comparison between measurements carried out in transmission suites and point mobility measurements, in: Canadian Acoustical Association, 2019.
- [128] M. Stewart, Surface Production Operations, Elsevier Ltd., 2016.
- [129] M. Tiso, Charring behavior of cross laminated timber with respect to the fire protection: Comparison of different methods in small, model and large scale with simulations, SP Technical Research Institute of Sweden, 2014.
- [130] F. Asdrubali, J.P. Arenas, Eco-Materials with Noise Reduction Properties, Handbook of Ecomaterials. (2017). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-48281-1_137-1.
- [131] F. Asdrubali, SURVEY ON THE ACOUSTICAL PROPERTIES OF NEW SUSTAINABLE MATERIALS FOR NOISE CONTROL, in: Tampere, Finland, 2006.
- [132] L. Wang, H. Ge, Hygrothermal performance of cross-laminated timber wall assemblies: A stochastic approach, Building Environment. 97 (2015) 11–25.
- [133] Greenspec, Insulation materials and their thermal properties, <Http://Www.Greenspec.Co.Uk/>. (n.d.). <http://www.greenspec.co.uk/building-design/insulation-materials-thermal-properties/>.
- [134] M. Pavelek, M. Prajer, K. Trgala, Static and Dynamic Thermal Characterization of Timber Frame/Wheat (Triticum Aestivum) Chaff Thermal Insulation Panel for Sustainable Building Construction, Sustainability. 10 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10072363>.
- [135] X. Zhu, B.-J. Kim, Q. Wang, Q. Wu, Recent Advances in the Sound Insulation Properties of Bio-based materials, BioResources. 9 (2013) 1764–1786.
- [136] N. Dauchez, M. Etchessahar, S. Sahraoui, On measurement of mechanical properties of sound absorbing materials, in: 2002.
- [137] X. Olny, R. Panneton, Acoustical determination of the parameters governing thermal dissipation in porous media, J. Acoust. Soc. Am. 123 (2008) 814–824. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.2828066>.

- [138] U. Berardi, R. Ramakrishnan, Comparison of the acoustic behaviour of porous materials in compressed and uncompressed conditions, in: 22nd International Congress on Acoustics, Buenos Aires, 2016.
- [139] H.-R. Kymalainen, A.-M. Sjöberg, Flax and hemp fibres as raw materials for thermal insulations, *Building and Environment*. 43 (2008) 1261–1269. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2007.03.006>.
- [140] C.M. HELEPCIUC (GRĂDINARU)*, SHEEP WOOL – A NATURAL MATERIAL USED IN CIVIL ENGINEERING, *BULETINUL INSTITUTULUI POLITEHNIC DIN IAȘI*. 63 (2017).
- [141] M. Liu, Y. Sun, C. Sun, X. Yang, STUDY ON THERMAL INSULATION AND HEAT TRANSFER PROPERTIES OF WOOD FRAME WALLS, *Wood REsearch*. 63 (2018) 249–260.
- [142] ThermoWorks, Infrared Emissivity Table, <https://www.thermoworks.com/>. (n.d.). <https://www.thermoworks.com/emissivity-table>.
- [143] P. Bonfiglio, F. Pompoli, K.V. Horoshenkov, M.I.B.S.A. Rahim, L. Jaouen, J. Rodenas, F.-X. Bécot, E. Gourdon, D. Jaeger, V. Kursch, How reproducible are methods to measure the dynamic viscoelastic properties of poroelastic media?, *Journal of Sound and Vibration*. 428 (2018) 26–43.
- [144] P. Bonfiglio, F. Pompoli, Inversion problems for determining physical parameters of porous materials: Overview and comparison between different methods, *Acta Acustica United with Acustica*. 99 (2013) 341–351.
- [145] R. Foret, C. Guigou-Carter, J.-B. Chene, Porous Material parameters influencing the acoustic performances of building construction systems, (2010).
- [146] U. Berardi, G. Iannace, Predicting the sound absorption of natural materials: Best-fit inverse laws for the acoustic impedance and the propagation constant, *Applied Acoustics*. 115 (2017) 131–138. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apacoust.2016.08.012>.
- [147] P. Glè, T. Blinet, C. Guigou-Carter, Acoustic performance prediction for building elements including biobased fibrous materials, in: EAA – HELINA, Crete, Greece, 2018: pp. 1659–1666.
- [148] A. Santoni, P. Bonfiglio, P. Fausti, C. Marescotti, V. Mazzanti, F. Mollica, F. Pompoli, Improving the sound absorption performance of sustainable thermal insulation materials: Natural hemp fibres, *Applied Acoustics*. 150 (2019) 279–289.
- [149] C. Debeleac, P. Nechita, S. Nastac, Computational Investigations on Soundproof Applications of Foam-Formed Cellulose Materials, *Polymers*. 11 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym11071223>.
- [150] E. Taban, A. Khavanin, M. Faridan, A.K. Tabrizi, Experimental and mathematical survey of sound absorption performance of date palm fibers, *Helyon*. 5 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.helyon.2019.e01977>.
- [151] K. Fabbri, L. Tronchin, F. Barbieri, Coconut fibre insulators: The hygrothermal behaviour in the case of green roofs, *Construction and Building Materials*. 266 (2021) 121026. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2020.121026>.
- [152] F. Nocera, A. Gagliano, M. Detommaso, Energy performance of cross-laminated timber panel (X-Lam) buildings: A case study, *Mathematical Modelling of Engineering Problems*. 5 (2018) 175–182. <https://doi.org/10.18280/mmep.050307>.
- [153] J. Niederwestberg, J. Zhou, Y.-H. Chui, Mechanical Properties of Innovative, Multi-Layer Composite Laminated Panels, *Buildings*. 8 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings8100142>.
- [154] J. Sliseris, L. Gaile, L. Pakrašiņš, Numerical analysis of behaviour of cross laminated timber (CLT) in blast loading, *Materials Science and Engineering*. 251 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/251/1/012105>.
- [155] International Organization for Standardization: Geneva, Switzerland, ISO 10140-5:2021 Acoustics — Laboratory measurement of sound insulation of building elements — Part 5: Requirements for test facilities and equipment., (2021).
- [156] European Committee for Standardization, Brussels, UNI EN 15425 (2017), Adhesives - One Component Polyurethane (PUR) for Load-Bearing Timber Structures - Classification and Performance Requirements. (n.d.).

- [157] European Committee for Standardization, Brussels, EN 338 (2016), Structural Timber–Strength Classes. (n.d.).
- [158] International Organization for Standardization: Geneva, Switzerland, ISO 10140-1:2021 Acoustics -- Laboratory measurement of sound insulation of building elements Application rules for specific products., (2021).
- [159] International Organization for Standardization: Geneva, Switzerland, ISO 10140-2:2021 Acoustics -- Laboratory measurement of sound insulation of building elements Measurement of airborne sound insulation., (2021).
- [160] International Organization for Standardization: Geneva, Switzerland, ISO 10140-3:2021 Acoustics — Laboratory measurement of sound insulation of building elements — Part 3: Measurement of impact sound insulation., (2021).
- [161] International Organization for Standardization: Geneva, Switzerland, ISO 10140-4:2021 Acoustics — Laboratory measurement of sound insulation of building elements — Part 4: Measurement procedures and requirements., (2021).
- [162] J. Olsson, A. Linderholt, Measurements of low frequency impact sound frequency response functions and vibrational properties of light weight timber floors utilizing the ISO rubber ball, Applied Acoustics. 166 (2020) 107313.
- [163] F.J. Fahy, P. Gardonio, Sound and structural vibration: radiation, transmission and response, Elsevier, 2007.
- [164] International Organization for Standardization: Geneva, Switzerland, ISO 717-1:2020 Acoustics — Rating of sound insulation in buildings and of building elements — Part 1: Airborne sound insulation, (2020).
- [165] International Organization for Standardization, ISO 717-2:2020 Acoustics — Rating of sound insulation in buildings and of building elements — Part 2: Impact sound insulation, (2021).
- [166] UNI, 10339 - Air-conditioning systems for thermal comfort in buildings. General classification and requirements - Offer, order and supply specifications, (1995).
- [167] ISO, 13790 - Energy performance of buildings. Calculation of energy use for space heating and cooling, (2008).